

D4.5. Protocol for Mobilizing Funding and Ensuring Sustainability – Final Version

June 2026

Inês Francisco
Tânia Moreira
Sara Carneiro

Document details	
Project Acronym / Name	CROPS: Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe
Project URL	http://crops-cs.eu
Project Type	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
EU Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Grant Agreement No.	101131696
Project Start Date	1 January 2024
Project end date	31 December 2026
Work Package	
Work Package	WP4 - Orchestration: Maximising uptake and sustainability when upscaling CS
Deliverable	D4.5. Protocol for mobilising funding and ensuring sustainability – Final Version
Due date of Deliverable	30/06/2026
Actual Submission date	30/06/2026
Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable	Inês Francisco, Tânia Moreira, Sara Carneiro (INOVA+)
Reviewed by	Todd Harwell (IIASA)
Version	1.0
Dissemination level	Public
Number of pages	93

Document history			
Version	Date	Comment	Modification made by
0.1	01/03/2026	D4.5's First version, updating D4.4 with inputs from stakeholder feedback	Inês Francisco, Tânia Moreira, Sara Carneiro (INOVA+)
0.2	23/06/2026	Revision	Todd Harwell (IIASA)
1.0	30/06/2026	Final version	Inês Francisco, Tânia Moreira, Sara Carneiro (INOVA+)

To cite this document:

I. Francisco, T. Moreira, S. Carneiro (2026). Deliverable 4.5: Protocol for mobilising funding and ensuring sustainability – Final Version. *Deliverable report of project Horizon Europe CROPS (grant agreement No. 101131696)*.

Acknowledgements

We want to express our deepest gratitude to everyone that accepted to participate and contribute to our work by responding to our surveys, interviews, group discussions or conversations. This document is stronger because of your candour and practical insight. Our sincere THANK YOU.

Copyright

© Partners of the CROPS Consortium, 2026

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

List of Tables	6
List of Figures	6
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 Context and purpose	9
1.2 Scope and approach	10
1.3 Key definitions.....	12
1.4. How to use this document.....	13
2 STEP 1: Know Your Possible Funding Landscape.....	16
2.1 How citizen science is funded today.....	16
2.2 Two lenses that shape every funding decision.....	18
2.3 The four funding categories used in this protocol.....	20
3 STEP 2: Diagnose Where You Are.....	22
4 STEP 3: Assess Whether an Opportunity Fits.....	25
5 Step 4: Develop Your Funding Model.....	28
6 Step 5: Choose and Pursue Your Funding Model	30
6.1 Public funding	30
6.2 Private funding.....	34
6.3 Crowdfunding	40
6.4 Hybrid funding	45
6.5 Transition planning: moving between models	52
7 Step 6: Build the Foundations and Sustain	54
7.1 Building funding intelligence and visibility	54
7.2 Linking evaluation design to funder communication	54
7.3 Communicating with different funders	55
7.4 Cross-cutting considerations: AI, data governance and ethics.....	57
7.5 Funding the invisible systems	58
8 Recommendations	60
8.1 For funders and funding agencies	60
8.2 For policymakers and public authorities	61
8.3 For host institutions and universities	62
8.4 For the wider CS ecosystem.....	62
9 Conclusions.....	63
10 References	67
10.1 Additional sources consulted.....	69

Annexes	71
Annexes	71
ANNEX A	71
Interview Protocols	71
A.1 Interview protocol, round 1 (semi-structured)	71
A.2 Interview protocol, round 2.....	72
Survey Instruments	72
B.1 CROPS Case Study Survey	72
B.2 Scalability Survey	72
Practical Business-Model Setup Guidance	73
The Funding Toolkit	75
D.1 Theory of Change template	75
D.2 Business Model Canvas (adapted for CS)	76
D.3 Value Proposition Canvas	77
D.4 SWOT Analysis	77
D.5 Funding Readiness Checklist.....	78
D.6 Funding Pipeline and Call Tracker	79
D.5 Funding Readiness Checklist.....	79
D.6 Funding Pipeline and Call Tracker	80
D.7 Data Management Plan template	81
D.8 Ethics and CS Principles Checklist.....	81
D.9 MICS (Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science) summary.....	82
D.10 SROI (Social Return on Investment) guidance.....	82
D.11 CS Funding Pitch Deck template.....	83
D.12 Sustainability and Transition Plan template.....	84
D.13 Partnership Due Diligence Checklist (for private and hybrid funding).....	85
D.14 Post-Grant Continuity Checklist	86
Anonymised List of Interviewees and Workshop Participants	87
Expert interviews, Round 1 (2025)	87
Expert interviews, Round 2 (2026)	88
Consolidated List of CROPS Empirical Data Sources	89
Glossary	90
Platforms for Networking, Visibility and Funding Intelligence	91

List of Tables

Table 1.1 Scope and Approach	11
Table 2.1. Comprehensive mapping of CS funding models	17
Table 2.2. Funding categories used in this protocol	20
Table 3.1. Stages of project maturity.....	22
Table 3.2. Scaling dimensions and their funding implications.....	23
Table 4.1. Funding Fit Framework Assessment: five dimensions	25
Table 4.2. Funding Fit Self-Assessment Test.....	26
Table 6.1. Business models relevant to CS funding and sustainability	47
Table 6.2. CS organisations generating economic value (selected ECS examples).....	49
Table 7.1. Communication approaches by funder type.....	55

List of Figures

• Figure 1 CROPS Funding Protocol Six Steps	14
---	----

Executive Summary

Citizen science (CS) is now recognised as an important part of European research and innovation. It helps produce useful data, connects research with society, and gives citizens a more active role in scientific work. However, many citizen science initiatives still face a serious problem: they are difficult to sustain once project funding ends.

This deliverable, **D4.5**, presents the final **CROPS Protocol for Mobilising Funding and Ensuring Sustainability**, designed to help citizen science projects understand their funding options, choose the most suitable routes, and plan for long-term sustainability. It builds on the earlier CROPS mapping of citizen science funding models (**D4.3**) and on feedback gathered through interviews, workshops, roundtables, and validation activities.

Most citizen science initiatives still depend heavily on short-term public grants. These grants are essential, especially for research-oriented projects, but they rarely solve the sustainability problem on their own. When a grant ends, projects often struggle to maintain the systems that made the work possible in the first place: coordination, communication, IT maintenance, data validation, community support, legal hosting, and feedback to participants. These “invisible systems” are often treated as overheads, but they are in fact core infrastructure. Without them, participation becomes harder to manage, data quality weakens, communities lose

trust, and successful projects may disappear.

The protocol organises funding options into four main categories:

1. **Public funding** includes EU, national, regional, and local grants, as well as cascading funding. It remains the most common route for citizen science, but it is usually time-limited and competitive.
2. **Private funding** includes foundations, companies, CSR or ESG programmes, industry partnerships, corporate volunteering, and paid services. It can support sustainability, but only when there is a clear value proposition and strong ethical safeguards.
3. **Crowdfunding** can help projects raise visibility, test public interest, or fund specific items such as kits, tools, or pilot activities. It should usually be treated as a complementary funding route, not as the main source of income.
4. **Hybrid funding** combines several sources, such as public grants, private partnerships, institutional support, service income, crowdfunding, and in-kind contributions. It can be more resilient, but it also requires stronger coordination, governance, and strategic focus.

To guide projects through these options, the protocol proposes a six-step process.

- **Step 1** helps projects understand the funding landscape and the different expectations of funders.
- **Step 2** supports an honest diagnosis of where the project stands: early-stage, established, or mature. It also asks how the project is trying to scale: geographically, institutionally, deeply within communities, or through a deliberate reduction in scope.
- **Step 3** provides a Funding Fit Framework to decide whether a specific opportunity is worth pursuing. It looks at mission fit, readiness, value proposition, capacity, and evidence of impact.
- **Step 4** helps projects build a funding model deliberately instead of reacting to whatever call or opportunity appears next.
- **Step 5** gives practical guidance for public funding, private funding, crowdfunding, and hybrid funding, including how projects can move from one model to another over time.
- **Step 6** focuses on the foundations that make funding sustainable: funding intelligence, visibility, evaluation, communication, AI, data governance, ethics, and the operational systems that support participation.

Projects should not chase funding at any cost. A funding opportunity may look attractive but still be wrong for the project if it creates mission drift, overloads the

team, weakens participant trust, or requires evidence and management capacity the project does not yet have.

For early or grassroots projects, the best starting points are often small grants, cascading funding, local support, crowdfunding, or partnerships. For established projects, competitive public grants and targeted partnerships become more realistic. For mature projects, hybrid models may provide more resilience, especially when they combine public-interest funding with services, institutional support, or carefully managed private partnerships.

The deliverable also includes recommendations for funders, policymakers, universities, host institutions, and the wider citizen science ecosystem.

The final conclusion is that citizen science cannot be sustained by enthusiasm alone. Volunteers contribute time, knowledge, data, and trust, but participation is not free. It depends on coordination, infrastructure, ethical governance, communication, and long-term relationships.

Projects that rely on a single short-term grant and fail to fund these systems are unlikely to last. Projects that plan funding from the beginning, budget honestly, protect their mission, and build strong relationships with funders and institutions have a better chance of creating lasting impact.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context and purpose

Citizen science (CS), the practice of actively involving the public in scientific inquiry and data generation, has gained increasing recognition for its ability to produce valuable data, strengthen the societal relevance of research, and support public engagement in scientific processes. CS has moved from the margins of research practice to a recognised pillar of European science policy. The European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda, under Action 14, calls for bringing science closer to citizens, and the Horizon Europe programme increasingly positions citizen science as a mechanism for addressing societal challenges through the five EU Missions. **Yet many CS initiatives face an ongoing challenge: securing stable and diversified funding, and ensuring long-term sustainability beyond project-based cycles.** Projects that produce credible science and build committed communities can still collapse when a grant ends, because the systems that make participation possible (coordination, platform hosting, data validation, community management, legal hosting) were never treated as core infrastructure worth sustaining.

CROPS¹ project aims to support the upscaling¹ of citizen science initiatives across Europe. One of its central commitments is to define a protocol that supports CS initiatives to mobilise the funds needed for sustainability, built on the experience of those in the field, and to deliver guidance for obtaining suitable funding and creating sustainable practices when upscaling citizen science activities.

This deliverable, D4.5, responds to that commitment. It provides a practical protocol to help CS projects navigate the abovementioned challenges. It is the final version of the funding mobilisation protocol developed under Task 4.4 of WP4 (*Orchestration: Maximising Uptake and Sustainability when Upscaling CS*), building on D4.4 (the preliminary version circulated to stakeholders at M24) and incorporating feedback from the later interviews, validation group discussions, and updated evidence.

The protocol is designed primarily for CS practitioners, project coordinators, and the people who write and manage their funding, though it also addresses funders, policymakers, host institutions, and researchers directly in its recommendation chapters.

D4.5 builds directly on two earlier CROPS deliverables:

- **D4.3, Mapping of CS Funding Models** (December 2025): the empirical baseline that mapped funding sources, prevalence, sustainability potential, and suitability across the CS landscape. This protocol simplifies and applies that taxonomy.

¹ Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe, GA 101131696, <https://crops-cs.eu/>.

- **D4.4, Protocol for Mobilising Funding and Ensuring Sustainability, Preliminary Version (M24):** the draft circulated to stakeholders for feedback. D4.5 is the final version that incorporates that feedback, the CROPS validation group discussions, and additional evidence collected during 2026.

The protocol is structured as a practical manual. Evidence from interviews, workshops, roundtables, and the literature supports each recommendation at the point where the reader needs it. A CS coordinator can open any section, find the funding route relevant to their situation, and act on it.

1.2 Scope and approach

The protocol draws on a targeted literature review and primary qualitative research. The evidence comes from CS practitioners, funders, platform operators, and experts from related fields:

- **Literature review.** A targeted review of peer-reviewed and grey literature on funding models, social entrepreneurship, impact assessment, and CS sustainability was conducted. Sources included academic articles (e.g., Foster, Kim and Christiansen, 2009; Kim, Perreault and Foster, 2011; Shirk et al., 2012; Kieslinger et al., 2018; Wehn et al., 2021; Mollick, 2014; Sauermann, Franzoni and Shafi, 2019; Mendell, 2010; Austin and Reficco, 2009; Battilana et al., 2012; Mitra et al., 2020; François and Goi, 2023; Fraisl et al., 2025), EU and project reports (COESO D4.1; DITOs D6.6; IMPETUS policy briefs; MLE Report 2022; ECSA position papers; Schürz et al., 2026; OECD, 2025), and recent work on AI and citizen science (Ceccaroni et al., 2019; Fortson et al., 2024; Lotfian et al., 2026). Every source cited in-text appears in the reference list (Chapter 10).
- **Expert interviews.** Seventeen (17) semi-structured interviews were conducted across two rounds. The first round (May - November 2025) covered nine experts whose insights also fed into D4.3. The second round (April - May 2026) expanded the evidence base with eight additional interviews, including platform leads (Zooniverse, Experiment.com), intermediary organisations (OutBe, Earthwatch), a public research funder (NWO, the Netherlands), and project-level practitioners from COESO/VERA and other initiatives. The full list of interviewees (anonymised where requested) is provided in **Annex E**. The interview protocol is reproduced in **Annex A**.
- **Expert Group validation discussions.** Five group discussions were organised with approximately 50 experts: three assuming the format of facilitated mutual learning and validation workshops organised within major events open to all interested participants (ECCN, ECSA, CAPS); other two assuming the format of dedicated expert roundtables open only for invited experts (see **Annex E** for more details on the validation discussions).

- CROPS WP2’s validation workshops.** Framework-validation sessions conducted as part of WP2 provided additional evidence on sustainability mechanisms and risks observed across CROPS case-study projects. Notes from these sessions were used as a supplementary source, particularly for the practical examples in Step 3 and for the discussion of infrastructure costs.

Table 1.1 Scope and Approach

Expert interviews	Round 1: Online May - November 2025	8 participants
	Round 2: Online April - May 2026	9 participants
Expert group validation discussions <i>Five group discussions were organised with approximately 50 experts</i>	Mutual learning and validation workshops:	
	Encontro Nacional de Ciência Cidadã Oeiras, Portugal November 2025	25 participants
	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) Conference 2026 Oulu, Finland March 2026	15 participants
	Conference for Advancing Participatory Sciences Online May 2026	10 participants
	Expert Roundtables	
	Round 1: Online April 2026	4 participants
	Round 2: Online May 2026	2 participants
CROPS WP2 validation workshops	February-April 2026 Online	30 participants
Total		103 participants

Analysis. The Inputs from literature, interviews, groups discussions and workshops, were analysed using a qualitative, thematic approach. Transcripts and notes were organised into thematic categories (funding models, sustainability strategies, cross-cutting challenges, social

entrepreneurship concepts, policy barriers). Findings were cross-referenced across sources to identify convergences, divergences, and gaps.

1.3 Key definitions

The following definitions apply throughout this protocol.

Term	Definition
Citizen science	The practice of actively involving members of the public in scientific research, whether in data collection, analysis, interpretation, question formulation, or study design (Haklay et al., 2021). The term is used broadly here, encompassing contributory, collaborative, and co-created models of participation (Shirk et al., 2012). The protocol is also relevant to projects using related terms such as participatory science, community science, or community-based monitoring.
Funding model	The combination of revenue sources, funder types, and decision-making logics through which a project or organisation secures the financial resources it needs to operate. A single project may rely on one funding model or combine several.
Business model	A broader concept than a funding model: it describes how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value, including its partnerships, activities, resources, cost structure, and value propositions, not only where the money comes from. In the context of CS, business models may include open data combined with paid services, knowledge brokerage, co-production cost models, or federated infrastructure membership, among others.
Sustainability	The ability to maintain the public value, community trust, useful knowledge, and core activities of a project or initiative over time, through appropriate institutional, financial, and governance arrangements. Sustainability is not the same as indefinite growth or permanent operation; it may also mean that methods, tools, datasets, or participatory approaches are reused, embedded in institutions, or adapted in new contexts.
Upscaling	Extending the reach, impact, or operational scope of a CS initiative. Following the CROPS framework (Sprinks et al., 2024, 2026; Radicchi et al., 2023), this involves four dimensions: scaling out (geographic replication across new sites or countries), scaling up (institutional embedding and policy influence), scaling deep (strengthening the quality and depth of participation, including cultural change and trust-building), and scaling down (deliberate reduction in scope when that best serves the mission or when resources are constrained). Each dimension has distinct funding implications (see Step 2). For detailed upscaling protocols, see CROPS D3.1 (Fraisl et al., 2026).
Hybrid funding	A funding approach that deliberately combines multiple types of funding sources (e.g. public grants, private partnerships, crowdfunding, service-based income, in-kind support) within a managed strategy. Hybrid

funding is not the same as simply having multiple ad hoc income streams; it implies deliberate coordination, governance, and strategic coherence.

1.4. How to use this document

This protocol is built around a six-step sequence that takes a project from understanding the funding environment to securing and sustaining support. Step 1 maps the landscape. Step 2 diagnoses where the project stands. Step 3 tests whether a specific opportunity is worth pursuing. Step 4 turns that judgement into a deliberate funding model. Step 5 gives route-specific guidance for pursuing public, private, crowdfunding, and hybrid funding, including transitions between them. Step 6 covers the operational foundations that decide whether funding can be won, managed, and renewed. The steps are sequential in logic but iterative in practice: as a project evolves, coordinators return to earlier steps and adjust their choices. Each step is written to stand alone, so a coordinator who already knows the landscape and has diagnosed their readiness can move straight to the route-specific guidance in Step 5.

The deliverable is organised as follows:

- **Chapter 1 (Introduction)** sets the context, explains the methodology, and defines key terms.
- **Chapters 2 to 7 (Steps 1 to 6)** form the core of the document. They present a six-step process for mobilising funding:
 1. **Step 1: Know Your Funding Landscape (Chapter 2)** summarises the CROPS D4.3 empirical mapping of CS funding models, introduces two analytical lenses (the beneficiary-funder distinction and the participation-funding link), presents the four funding categories used throughout this protocol (public, private, crowdfunding, and hybrid), and states plainly how far the field still depends on public grants.
 2. **Step 2: Diagnose Where You Are (Chapter 3)** sets out a three-stage maturity model and shows how a project’s scaling direction shapes what its funding needs to cover.
 3. **Step 3: Assess Whether an Opportunity Fits (Chapter 4)** provides the Funding Fit Framework, a five-dimension test with a scored self-assessment for deciding whether a given opportunity is worth scarce capacity.
 4. **Step 4: Develop Your Funding Model (Chapter 5)** turns the diagnosis and fit assessment into a deliberate model using a structured six-step process.
 5. **Step 5: Choose and Pursue Your Funding Model (Chapter 6)** provides practical, route-specific guidance on public, private, crowdfunding, and hybrid funding,

and closes with guidance on planning transitions between models. Within Step 5, each funding model section follows the same internal structure, so a reader always knows where to look:

- **What practitioners say:** short, attributed quotes from CROPS interviews and workshops.
- **When this model fits.**
- **What needs to be in place first.**
- **Recommended actions:** direct, instructional guidance.
- **Common risks and trade-offs.**
- **What to do when things go wrong.**
- **Insight from the literature.**
- **At a glance:** a short summary box.

6. **Step 6: Build the Foundations and Sustain (Chapter 7)** covers the operational foundations common to every route: funding intelligence and visibility, linking evaluation to funder communication, AI, data governance and ethics, and funding the invisible systems that sustainability depends on.

Figure 1 CROPS Funding Protocol Six Steps

The steps are sequential in logic but iterative in practice: as a project evolves, coordinators return to earlier steps, revisit their funding strategy, and adjust their choices.

- **Chapter 8 (What Funders and Policymakers Can Do)** sets out recommendations for funders and funding agencies, policymakers and public authorities, host institutions and universities, and the wider CS ecosystem.
- **Chapter 9 (Conclusions and Next Steps)** draws together the headline conclusions of D4.3 and D4.5, states the practical bottom line for practitioners and funders, and links the protocol to the CROPS uptake targets (KPI #10 and KPI #11).
- **Chapter 10 (References)** provides the full reference list.

- **The Annexes (A to H)** contain the interview protocols, survey instruments, business-model setup guidance, the practical toolkit (Theory of Change, Business Model Canvas, Value Proposition Canvas, SWOT, Funding Readiness Checklist, and other templates), an anonymised list of interviewees and workshop participants, a consolidated list of CROPS empirical data sources, a glossary, and a directory of funding and visibility platforms (Annex H).

2 STEP 1: Know Your Possible Funding Landscape

Before choosing a funding route, a project needs to understand what options exist, what funders care about, and where citizen science sits in the broader funding ecosystem. This chapter summarises the empirical mapping conducted in CROPS D4.3 and introduces two analytical lenses that shape every funding decision: the beneficiary-funder distinction and the link between participation design and funding logic.

2.1 How citizen science is funded today

The CROPS D4.3 mapping (Moreira and Francisco, 2025) analysed funding sources, prevalence, sustainability potential, and suitability across the European CS landscape. Its central finding is clear: **CS funding is dominated by short-term competitive public grants**, while alternative models remain underdeveloped or unevenly accessible.

Competitive EU grants (Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe) are by far the most common funding source for research-oriented CS, but their sustainability potential is low because funding ends with the project and requires continuous reapplication. National and regional public programmes are moderately prevalent and variable in duration. Cascading grants (Financial Support to Third Parties, FSTP) are growing as an entry point for smaller initiatives but remain project-dependent. Private funding through corporate CSR, industry partnerships, or philanthropic foundations is still rare in CS, though its sustainability potential is higher when partnerships are rooted in a company's core operations rather than discretionary budgets. Crowdfunding is very rarely used, yields modest amounts (on Experiment.com, the median campaign target is around USD 3,500, with successful campaigns raising a median of roughly USD 3,100; Sauermann, Franzoni and Shafi, 2019), and calls for sustained communications effort. Membership and subscription models can provide predictable recurring revenue but require an established, engaged community. Hybrid models combining several of these sources characterise the most sustainable initiatives, though they require coordination capacity that many projects lack.

The evidence from the European Citizen Science (ECS) Impact Book (Schürz et al., 2026) reinforces this picture and adds a necessary qualification: economic value in CS should be understood beyond direct funding attraction. CS can generate services, trusted data, digital infrastructure, consultancy, tourism and education offers, training activities, and innovation partnerships, particularly where projects combine public grants with complementary revenue streams. The strongest economic case tends to be indirect and conditional: CS creates innovation capacity, service development, trusted datasets, public legitimacy, and institutional learning, rather than straightforward financial returns.

Table 2.1 provides the comprehensive mapping from D4.3.

Table 2.1. Comprehensive mapping of CS funding models

Category	Model	Description	Prevalence	Sustainability	Best Suited For
Public/EU Grants	Competitive Grants (EU)	Peer-reviewed funding for defined project periods (H2020, HE)	Very High	Low: ends with grant; requires continuous reapplication	Research-oriented CS; university-led projects; technology development
	National/Regional Public	Research councils, regional authorities, government programmes	Moderate	Variable: some ongoing programmes exist	Nationally-focused CS; environmental monitoring; policy-linked data
	Cascading Grants (FSTP)	Sub-grants from larger EU projects with simplified requirements	Growing	Low: project-dependent; but good entry point	New/small initiatives; grassroots projects; capacity building
Private Sector	Corporate CSR	Corporate social responsibility programmes	Low	Variable: depends on corporate priorities	Tech-enabled CS; projects with visibility/PR value
	Industry Partnership	Commercial contracts or revenue-sharing arrangements	Very Low	High if established: recurring revenue possible	Data-generating CS; gaming integrations; sensor networks
Philanthropic	Foundation Grants	Grants from private foundations, often theme-focused	Low	Moderate: flexible but unpredictable	Thematically-aligned CS (environment, health); Global South
Crowdfunding	Online Campaigns	Campaigns for specific projects (Kickstarter, Experiment.com)	Very Low	Low: one-time; median ~\$3,500; high effort	Pilot projects; community-embedded initiatives; bridge funding
Membership	Membership/Subscription	Regular contributions from engaged community members	Low-Mod	High: predictable revenue if community established	Established NGOs; conservation CS; long-running programmes
Hybrid	Diversified Model	Combination of multiple funding sources	Low	High: resilience through diversification	Mature organisations; long-term initiatives

	Social Enterprise	Revenue from services (training, products, consulting)	Very Low	High if viable: self-sustaining model	Technology providers; consultancy-capable organisations
In-Kind	In-Kind Support	Cloud computing, engineering time, equipment, volunteer labour	Supplementary	Variable: reduces costs but not standalone	Tech-dependent CS; partnerships with tech companies
	Institutional Base	University or research institute core funding	Moderate	Moderate: stable while institutionally embedded	Academic-led CS; teaching-linked initiatives

Source: D4.3 Mapping of Citizen Science funding models

One caution from CROPS’ own evidence: not all models in this mapping are equally accessible to every project. CS remains heavily dependent on short-term public grants, and the alternatives are underdeveloped or unevenly available. A small grassroots initiative, a one-off thematic project, a long-term monitoring programme, and a multi-project platform do not face the same constraints and should not be expected to rely on the same models. Diversification is often presented as a universal solution, but in practice it is realistic only for organisations with stable core capacity. For many projects the honest answer is that public funding will remain the primary source, and the practical question is how to use it more strategically, by building institutional embedding, planning for continuity, and reducing dependence on a single grant cycle, rather than how to replace it.

A second caution concerns what the money is expected to cover. Sustainability failures often arise when projects fund visible activities but not the invisible systems that make them credible: coordination, IT maintenance, quality assurance, hosting, community support, and data stewardship. **Step 6** returns to this in detail; it is flagged here because it should shape funding choices from the outset.

2.2 Two lenses that shape every funding decision

Two analytical perspectives from the literature recur throughout this protocol and shape the logic of every recommendation that follows.

2.2.1 The beneficiary-funder distinction

A fundamental challenge for CS funding comes from the nonprofit funding literature. Foster, Kim and Christiansen (2009) observe that in mission-driven organisations, **the people who benefit from the work are often not the people who pay for it**. In CS, citizen participants are the primary beneficiaries of learning, empowerment, engagement, and community connection, but they are rarely the primary funders. Public agencies, private foundations, or

corporate partners are more likely to pay, and they may care about different kinds of value than participants receive.

This asymmetry has a practical consequence: **CS projects typically need to develop two distinct value propositions**, one for the communities and participants they serve, and one for the funders who make the work possible. Projects that conflate the two, or that present participation as the primary funding argument without connecting it to the priorities of the funder, risk weakening their case to all parties.

Wehn et al. (2021) add a further complication: **CS projects generate impact across multiple domains simultaneously** (science, economy, environment, society, governance), but different funders are interested in different domains. Public and EU grants tend to prioritise scientific and governance outcomes; private-sector and CSR funders tend to focus on societal and economic dimensions; community-based funding tends to reflect environmental and local social concerns. The mismatch between a project's actual impact profile and the impact domains most visible to a particular funder is one reason CS initiatives struggle to communicate their full value.

From the field: “Why are you ‘donating’ and you’re not ‘investing’? I feel like the paradigm should change in order to leverage private funding for citizen science.”
(*Expert interviews, May 2026*)

2.2.2 The participation-funding link

The degree and quality of public participation in a CS project also shapes its funding logic. Shirk et al. (2012) distinguish models of participation with different resource implications and appeal to different funders:

- **Contributory models**, where citizens primarily collect data within a researcher-designed framework, tend to generate large, standardised datasets. These are more easily fundable through traditional research grants and data-driven industry partnerships.
- **Collaborative and co-created models**, where citizens are involved in question formulation, study design, or data interpretation, generate stronger local relevance, community capacity, and policy influence. These may be better positioned to attract community-based support, civic crowdfunding, local government funding, or foundations focused on social impact.

Projects should therefore consider their participation model not only as a methodological choice but as a factor in their funding landscape. This does not mean designing participation around funders' preferences; it means understanding which funders are a natural fit for what the project already does, and communicating accordingly.

2.3 The four funding categories used in this protocol

Drawing on the D4.3 mapping and the analytical lenses above, this protocol organises its practical guidance around **four broad funding categories**, simplified from the more granular taxonomy in D4.3. Each category is addressed in **detail in Step 5 (Chapter 6)**.

Table 2.2. Funding categories used in this protocol

Category	Includes	Core logic
Public funding	EU competitive grants, national/regional programmes, cascading grants (FSTP), research-council funding, awards and prizes, government procurement.	Financial support distributed through public institutions, usually via competitive calls or policy-linked programmes. The dominant model in CS, but time-limited and administratively demanding.
Private funding	Corporate CSR and ESG programmes, industry partnerships, philanthropic foundations, service contracts, corporate volunteering, in-kind support.	Financial or material support from private actors. Requires a clear value proposition, ethical boundaries, and often a relationship-building process rather than a formal application.
Crowdfunding	Online campaign platforms, recurring supporter models, civic crowdfunding with match-funding, fee-for-kit or fee-for-service models, participant donations.	Funding from the project’s own community, supporters, or the wider public. Communications-intensive and best suited as a supplement or bridge, not as a primary funding source.
Hybrid funding	Any deliberate combination of public, private, community, service-based, and in-kind sources.	Coordinated use of multiple funding streams. Requires governance, relationship management, and strategic coherence. The most resilient model for mature projects, but also the most demanding.

These categories are not mutually exclusive. Most CS projects that achieve long-term sustainability rely on some form of hybrid approach. The categories are presented separately to give each its own practical section, but the transition planning section (4.5) addresses how projects move between them.

STEP 1 AT GLANCE: Know Your Possible Funding Landscape

- CS remains heavily dependent on short-term public grants. Alternative models exist but are unevenly developed.
- The CROPS D4.3 mapping identifies 12 distinct funding models across public, private, community, hybrid, and supplementary categories.
- Two analytical lenses shape every funding decision: (1) the beneficiary-funder distinction, which means CS projects need separate value propositions for participants and funders; and (2) the participation-funding link, which means the project's participation design influences which funders are a natural fit.
- Economic value in CS is real but should not be overclaimed. It is typically indirect: services, trusted data, digital infrastructure, consultancy, and institutional learning, rather than straightforward financial returns.
- Sustainability failures often arise from underfunding the invisible systems (coordination, IT, data stewardship, community support) that make participation credible.
- This protocol organises guidance around four categories: public funding, private funding, crowdfunding, and hybrid funding.

Go further...

- **CROPS D4.3, Mapping of CS Funding Models** (Moreira and Francisco, 2025): the full empirical mapping behind the summary in this chapter, including detailed analysis by funding type, prevalence, and project suitability.
- **COESO D4.1, Landscape study on funding schemes for SSH citizen science** (Pelacho et al., 2021): analysis of 105 funding bodies across Europe, with findings on discoverability barriers and structural gaps. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/5137247>
- **OECD (2025), Embedding citizen science into research policy**: policy paper covering six enabling factors for CS integration into national funding systems. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/04/embedding-citizen-science-into-research-policy_2e6e92e4/a1cfb1a8-en.pdf
- **Schürz et al. (2026), Beyond Participation**: the ECS Impact Book with case studies of CS organisations generating economic value. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20084379>
- **VERA Fundit** (vera.operas-eu.org/en/fundit): a dedicated funding-opportunity finder for CS projects, particularly in the social sciences and humanities.

3 STEP 2: Diagnose Where You Are

Funding strategy begins with an honest assessment of where the project actually stands. The route that suits a small volunteer group is rarely the route that suits an institutionally embedded platform, and pursuing the wrong one consumes capacity the project cannot spare. This step sets out a simple three-stage maturity model and shows how a project’s scaling direction shapes what its funding needs to cover.

Funding strategies for CS projects cannot be one-size-fits-all. The suitability of different funding routes depends on a project’s maturity, organisational capacity, evidence base, and ability to communicate its value. The following three-stage model, drawn from the CROPS expert interviews and roundtable discussions, provides an analytical framework for matching projects to appropriate funding opportunities. The stages are flexible categories rather than fixed thresholds.

From the field: Projects should clarify their legal and institutional host early in the scaling process. Whether a project is hosted by an NGO, university, company, public body, foundation, or informal network affects which funding routes are available. (CROPS WP2’s Validation Workshops, 2026)

Table 3.1. Stages of project maturity

DIAGNOSE WHERE YOU ARE	
Stage 1: Early or grassroots projects	<p>Realistic funding options at this stage are usually limited. Projects often lack dedicated staff, a strong institutional track record, or extensive evidence of impact. The most appropriate starting points include crowdfunding, small seed grants, cascading grants, or FSTP schemes, where eligibility requirements are less demanding than in large competitive programmes.</p> <p>The priority is not to secure large-scale funding immediately, but to demonstrate that the project exists, that there is public or community interest, and that it can deliver a modest but measurable outcome. Pursuing large competitive grants or complex private partnerships too early can be counterproductive, consuming time and energy the project cannot spare.</p>
Stage 2: Established or growing projects	<p>These projects usually have some evidence of activity, a clearer scientific or social rationale, emerging partnerships, and some form of institutional affiliation. Competitive public grants become realistic, particularly where the project can demonstrate a defined problem, a credible methodology, and measurable outcomes. Targeted private funding may also become appropriate where there is a genuine fit between the funder’s priorities and the project’s mission. Hybrid funding combinations may begin to make sense, such as using a</p>

	<p>public grant as a financial base while adding one private, philanthropic, or in-kind partnership.</p> <p>The main risk at this stage is overextension. Projects may be tempted to pursue several funding relationships at once, creating administrative pressure and reporting obligations that exceed the team’s capacity. Funding diversification should be gradual and strategic.</p>
Stage 3: Mature or institutionally embedded projects	<p>These projects tend to have a stable team, demonstrated outputs, established partnerships, and clearer evidence of scientific, social, environmental, or educational impact. Larger competitive grants, Horizon Europe applications, multi-partner collaborations, private-sector partnerships, consultancy services, and training activities may all become viable.</p> <p>The challenge shifts from access to coherence. The risk is no longer failing to attract funding, but losing strategic direction under the pressure of managing multiple streams simultaneously. Strong governance, clear ethical boundaries, transparent data and participant-rights policies, and regular feedback loops with communities are essential at this stage.</p>
	<p>A note on transitions: Projects do not stay at one stage. Moving between stages requires deliberate planning rather than chasing the next available opportunity. Section 6.5 covers the most common transition points in detail.</p>

3.1.1 Funding implications of different scaling directions

How a project scales affects what it costs and how it should be funded. The CROPS D3.1 (Protocols for Upscaling; Sprinks et al., 2026) distinguishes four scaling dimensions, each with distinct funding implications.

Table 3.2. Scaling dimensions and their funding implications

Scaling direction	What it means	Funding implications
Scaling out (geographic replication)	More sites, regions, countries	Needs multi-partner consortium funding, cascading grants for local nodes, or a hub-and-spoke model. Coordination, translation, and intermediary costs increase.
Scaling up (institutional embedding)	Policy influence, integration into public systems	Needs longer funding timelines, institutional base funding, and connections to policy-relevant programmes. Co-production cost models may become viable.

Scaling deep (cultural change)	Deeper participation, co-creation, capacity building	Needs funders who value participation quality over participant numbers. Foundations, community funds, and education grants may be more appropriate than large research calls.
Scaling down (deliberate reduction)	Reduced scope for quality or resource constraints	May reduce total funding need but requires transition planning (Section 6.5). Scaling down is a legitimate sustainability decision when it preserves public value.

Source: Scaling dimensions adapted from Radicchi et al. (2023) and Sprinks et al. (2024, 2026), as used in the CROPS project. See CROPS D3.1 for detailed upscaling protocols.

◀◀ STEP 2 AT GLANCE: Diagnose Where You Are

- Match funding ambitions to maturity. Early projects should start small and build a track record; established projects can add targeted streams; mature projects can manage hybrid models but need strong governance.
- A project’s scaling direction (out, up, deep, or down) changes what it costs and how it should be funded.
- Diagnosis is not a verdict on a project’s worth. It identifies which routes are realistic now and which require groundwork first.

4 STEP 3: Assess Whether an Opportunity Fits

Knowing your stage (Step 2) tells you which routes are plausible. It does not tell you whether a specific opportunity is worth your scarce capacity.

Before pursuing a funding route, CS projects should assess whether the opportunity fits the project across five areas. This framework synthesises insights from the CROPS expert interviews, roundtables, and the literature.

Table 4.1. Funding Fit Framework Assessment: five dimensions

Dimension 1: Mission, ethics and community fit	<p><i>Does this funder’s agenda align with our scientific purpose, participant rights, and community priorities?</i></p> <p>The project should assess whether the funder’s priorities align with its scientific purpose, public-interest commitments, participant rights, data governance, and community priorities. Revenue-generating models, corporate partnerships, or public funding routes should only be pursued where they do not create barriers for participants or weaken the project’s social mission.</p> <div style="background-color: #f0f0f0; padding: 5px; border: 1px solid #ccc;"> <p>Tip: In lower-income or resource-constrained contexts, ethical funding design may include paid roles, training, locally useful services, infrastructure, or health and safety improvements for participants, not only data extraction.</p> </div>
Dimension 2: Project-stage and readiness fit	<p><i>Are we early, established, or mature enough for this route?</i></p> <p>Projects should consider whether they are early, established, or mature enough for a given funding route (see Step 2). The key question is whether the funding opportunity matches the project’s current maturity, or whether pursuing it would consume capacity before the project is ready.</p>
Dimension 3: Value proposition and communication fit	<p><i>Can we explain clearly what we offer, to whom, and why the funder should care?</i></p> <p>Projects need to explain clearly, in accessible terms, what problem they address, what evidence or service they provide, who benefits, and why the funder should care. This requires more than describing data collection. The project should communicate its scientific, social, educational, environmental, or organisational value, including how it may influence awareness, behaviour, local practice, or policy. Communication expertise should be involved early, particularly to test whether people outside CS can understand the project’s purpose.</p>
Dimension 4: Capacity and sustainability fit	<p><i>Can we manage this funding without overloading the team? Have we budgeted for the hidden costs?</i></p> <p>A funding opportunity should be assessed against the team’s real ability to apply for, manage, report on, and sustain the funding without overloading staff or volunteers. Burnout is a funding risk, not an</p>

	<p>individual weakness. Projects should consider time, skills, communication capacity, partnership capacity, administrative support, and workload distribution before pursuing funding. Diversifying funding sources can improve resilience, but only if the process itself does not create unsustainable fundraising pressure.</p> <p>Funding readiness should explicitly include hidden administrative and IT costs. Scaling out increases participant support, missing-data follow-up, photo verification, data validation, platform hosting, troubleshooting, and coordination across sites. These are core delivery costs and should be budgeted as such (CROPS WP2’s Validation Workshops, 2026).</p>
<p>Dimension 5: Evidence, learning and impact fit</p>	<p><i>Do we have the metrics and documentation to demonstrate value over time?</i></p> <p>Projects should have appropriate metrics, feedback loops, and documentation processes in place to demonstrate value over time. This includes scientific outputs, participant engagement, community benefits, environmental or social outcomes, and financial sustainability. Regular feedback to participants is part of this dimension: contributors should see how their involvement matters and how results are used.</p>
<p> Warning. Funding readiness should include a “can this work evolve?” check. Assess not only whether the project can scale, but whether it <i>should</i> scale, refocus, pause, transfer, or stop. Sustainability is not the same as indefinite growth; it is the ability to preserve public value through the most appropriate arrangement (AAPS, CAPS 2026).</p>	

Table 4.2. Funding Fit Self-Assessment Test

Funding Fit Self-Assessment Test		
<p>Before pursuing a specific funding opportunity, score your project on each dimension (1 = not ready, 5 = fully ready). Be honest; this tool is for internal use.</p>		
Dimension	Question	Score (1-5)
1. Mission and ethics	The funder’s priorities align with our purpose, participant rights, and community values. We have defined our ethical boundaries.	—
2. Project stage	Our project is at the right maturity level for this route. We are not overreaching.	—
3. Value proposition	We can explain in two sentences what we offer, to whom, and why this funder should care. Someone outside CS would understand it.	—

4. Capacity	The team can manage the application, delivery, reporting, and relationship without overloading. We have budgeted for hidden costs.	___
5. Evidence and learning	We have metrics, documentation, and feedback processes in place. Evaluation is built in, not bolted on.	___
	Total	___ / 25

How to read your score. These bands are a practical heuristic drawn from the CROPS interviews and roundtables, not a validated measurement instrument. Treat the number as a prompt for an honest conversation, not a gate.

- 20-25: Strong fit. The main risk now is delivery, not eligibility. Proceed.
- 15-19: Partial fit. Identify which dimensions pulled the score down and address those before committing.
- 10-14: Probably not ready for this route. A simpler or smaller option will usually serve the project better right now.
- Below 10: Return to Step 2. The groundwork is not yet in place.

Two cautions. The pattern of scores matters more than the total: a project scoring 5 on mission but 1 on capacity is in a different position from one scoring 3 across the board, even at the same total. And the bands should be calibrated to context, since a small grassroots grant and a multi-partner EU call do not demand the same readiness. The scorecard makes a difficult judgement explicit; it does not make it for you.

Red flag rule: Any single dimension scoring 1 is a stop signal, regardless of the total.

5 Step 4: Develop Your Funding Model

With a clear read of your stage (Step 2) and a fit assessment of the opportunities in front of you (Step 3), you can develop a funding model deliberately rather than reacting to whichever call appears next. The process below turns those two inputs into a concrete plan.

Kim, Perreault and Foster (2011) offer a practical six-step framework for developing a sustainable funding model that translates directly to CS:

Kim et al. stress that funding model development is not a one-time exercise but a strategic process revisited as the project evolves. The right funding model is the one that fits the project's mission, capacity, and funder relationships. For CS, this means resisting the

temptation to diversify for its own sake and instead making deliberate, staged choices about which streams to develop and when.

◀◀ STEP 1 AT GLANCE: Know Your Possible Funding Landscape

- Treat funding-model development as a deliberate, repeatable process, not a one-off scramble: analyse current funding, learn from peers, shortlist options, evaluate them, select, and plan implementation.
- Feed the Step 2 diagnosis and the Step 3 fit assessment directly into steps 1 to 4 of this process.
- Resist diversifying for its own sake. Add a stream only when the project can carry the work it brings.

Go further...

- **Kim, Perreault and Foster (2011), Finding Your Funding Model:** the full Bridgespan Group guide on developing a sustainable funding model. Available at: <https://www.bridgespan.org/insights/nonprofit-financial-sustainability/finding-your-funding-model-a-practical-approach-to>

6 Step 5: Choose and Pursue Your Funding Model

This chapter is the core of the protocol. It provides practical guidance for each of the four funding categories identified in Step 1, followed by a section on transition planning. Each section follows the same structure so that a reader who needs only one can use it independently.

6.1 Public funding

6.1.1 What practitioners say

“Public funding is maybe not the most sustainable approach because there might not always be the right call for your project.” (Expert group validation discussions, March 2026)

“The competition is very high, and the funds are going down. There is a strategic work of connection to be done, especially for European funding.” (Expert group validation discussions, April 2026)

“We shouldn’t forget that citizen science is a methodology. It needs to fit into other areas, and it’s those other areas that will get the significant funding.” (Expert group validation discussions, April 2026)

“Sustainability is always a big issue because we are a temporary initiative. We have 10 years of funding, and we tend to do four-year programmes. We can’t do long-term funding unless it’s an infrastructure.” (Expert group validation discussions, May 2026)

6.1.2 When this model fits

Public funding is best suited to research-oriented CS projects, university-led initiatives, policy-linked monitoring activities, and projects that can clearly align with societal or scientific priorities. It is especially relevant for projects addressing biodiversity, climate, health, education, or environmental monitoring that can demonstrate both scientific and public value. Cascading grants (FSTP) are particularly useful for smaller, newer, or grassroots initiatives not yet ready to compete for large European calls directly.

CROPS workshops described a recurring funding trap: short grants can launch strong CS initiatives but then undermine continuity when coordination, data stewardship, IT maintenance, and community relationships remain unfunded after the project period.

6.1.3 What needs to be in place first

A project needs more than a socially attractive idea. It needs a clear scientific purpose, a well-defined value proposition, some understanding of the relevant policy or research landscape, and a credible plan for participation, delivery, and budgeting. For European funding, projects also need relationships: network-building is not optional but often a precondition for entry.

A structural dimension of this challenge deserves acknowledgement. The COESO D4.1 landscape study examining 105 funding bodies found that calls with small budgets per project, the scale most appropriate for locally grounded CS, are either very difficult to locate or simply do not exist (Pelacho et al., 2021). Among CS practitioners, the most commonly reported funding barrier was not competition or eligibility but discoverability: practitioners cannot find relevant calls at all. A further barrier for smaller organisations is the cost of co-designing proposals with partners before a grant is secured, unpaid preparation time that grassroots groups often cannot absorb.

 Warning. Public funding and procurement systems can reward organisations with legal infrastructure, compliance capacity, and audit-ready accounting while screening out grassroots groups. They also often require fixed scopes of work, which can conflict with iterative participatory science where communities help define what is measured and what outcomes matter (AAPS, CAPS 2026).

6.1.4 Recommended actions

1	Run a readiness self-assessment before applying	Decide whether the project is ready to lead, better placed as a partner, or better suited to a cascading/FSTP route. This prevents small teams from spending scarce capacity on calls they are not yet competitive for.
2	Define the scientific value as clearly as the social value	Public proposals should explain the research question, evidence gap, methodological contribution, expected knowledge gain, and relevance of the data produced. Participation alone is rarely enough in a competitive research-funding context.
3	Map the funding landscape beyond “citizen science” calls	Search for participatory research, co-creation, public engagement, environmental monitoring, health, education, climate adaptation, local resilience, cultural heritage, and regional development instruments. Consider municipal, regional, Interreg, ministry-led, and community investment schemes.
4	Decide strategically whether to lead, join, or support a consortium	Smaller initiatives may gain more by joining as a technical, methodological, or community partner than by coordinating a proposal independently
5	Budget for real delivery capacity	Include the true costs of volunteer mobilisation, facilitation, communications, coordination, participant support, data quality, evaluation, and overheads. Under-budgeted CS projects are fragile even when funded.

6	Separate core operations from new development in budgets	Mature CS platforms need resources for hosting, software maintenance, data validation, documentation, community management, and interoperability, not only for new deliverables. Public grants can create a sustainability trap when they finance new outputs but not ongoing base operations.
7	Establish impact metrics from the start (e.g. MICS, SROI)	Evaluation should be built into the proposal design, not added at reporting stage.
8	Build the institutional embedding case during seed funding	Use outputs, partnerships, events, and demonstrated demand to argue for base funding before the grant ends.
9	Plan continuity beyond the grant	Public funding is rarely sufficient on its own. Link early to the Hybrid Funding guidance (Section 6.4) and identify which activities can be sustained through institutional support, in-kind contributions, service-based work, or a reduced-cost continuation model.

6.1.5 Common risks and trade-offs

The biggest risk is over-adaptation to calls without clarity about the project’s own purpose. Another is presenting CS mainly as a social-good activity while underplaying the scientific rationale, which weakens the proposal in competitive research contexts. A further risk is weak impact measurement: projects that do not define social, scientific, environmental, and financial metrics early may struggle to demonstrate credibility. Public funding also creates a structural sustainability problem, since even successful projects may remain fragile if there is no plan for what happens when the grant ends.

6.1.6 What to do when things go wrong

If a public grant application is rejected, request feedback where the programme allows it. Map the gap between the application and the evaluation criteria. Decide whether the project is ready to reapply in the next cycle or whether it needs a period of consolidation first. Do not resubmit the same application without meaningful revision.

6.1.7 Insight from the literature

Public funders increasingly require CS projects to demonstrate impact beyond participation numbers. Kieslinger et al. (2018) offer a three-dimensional evaluation framework (scientific, participant-centred, socio-ecological/economic) that can structure credible reporting. The

OECD (2025), in its policy paper on embedding citizen science into research policy, identifies six enabling factors for CS to be integrated into national funding systems: the legal and policy environment, institutional research culture, capacity building and networks, supporting infrastructure, societal dialogue, and, centrally, the design and management of effective funding programmes. Projects that understand these systemic factors can position their proposals more effectively and advocate for structural change where needed.

◀◀ AT GLANCE: Public Funding

- Best for: research-oriented CS, university-led projects, policy-linked monitoring, and projects aligned with EU or national priorities.
- Key preparation: clear scientific rationale, relevant networks, realistic budget, evaluation plan from the start.
- Main risk: grant dependence without a continuity plan.
- Bottom line: approach public funding strategically, not as a self-sufficient solution. Plan for what comes after.

Go further...

- **EU Funding & Tenders Portal** (ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders): the central portal for Horizon Europe and EU Missions. Use the partner search tool to find consortium partners.
- **COESO D4.1** (Pelacho et al., 2021): landscape study of 105 funding bodies, directly relevant to finding CS calls.
- **MLE Report (2022)**: European Commission Mutual Learning Exercise on CS, including funding recommendations. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/63baa6bb-d359-11ed-a05c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- **ECSA Position Paper (2024)**: policy recommendations for CS in the next EU Framework Programme.
- **CROPS D3.3** (Moreira et al., 2026): for guidance on consortium partnerships and stakeholder relationships that public funding requires.

6.2 Private funding

6.2.1 What practitioners say

“The challenge with private funding lies in defining who the private funders are, including foundations and corporations. Projects need to position citizen science as a service to these funders, highlighting how citizen science can directly benefit businesses.” (Expert group validation discussions, March 2026)

“Citizen science, it’s not a favour, it could be a service itself.” (Expert group validation discussions, March 2026)

“Companies always need to answer questions, to research something, to innovate on something. Citizen science can help them to do so.” Expert interview, May 2026)

“The outcomes need to be examined against what’s promised and what actually happens from the funding partner.” (Expert interview, May 2026)

6.2.2 When this model fits

Private funding fits best when a project can offer something concrete to an external actor: community engagement, environmental visibility, employee activation, local legitimacy, data, participation design, or a problem-specific service. It works particularly well for mature projects, applied environmental or health initiatives, technology-enabled projects, and projects that can translate CS into something useful for a company, foundation, or mission-led organisation. It is less suitable when the project has no clear external value proposition.

Evidence from the ECS Impact Book (Schürz et al., 2026) supports this service framing. Private or mission-oriented actors are more likely to engage when CS produces practical value: trusted data, participation design, environmental intelligence, user feedback, digital infrastructure, or service models. Examples include MMOS through gaming integrations, Anèl-lides through blue education and marine monitoring, SPOTTERON through digital participation infrastructure, and STAB VIDA through biotechnology validation.

6.2.3 What needs to be in place first

Before pursuing private funding, a project needs clarity on three things: **who counts as a relevant private funder, what the project is offering, and where its ethical boundaries are.** Many CS projects understand grants and philanthropy loosely but become uncertain when dealing with private foundations, SMEs, or business-to-business collaboration. A project also needs to decide in advance what kinds of partnership it would reject, because once funding pressure rises, teams often rationalise compromises they would previously have refused.

Private funding outreach should not start from the message “we need money.” It should start from a clear explanation of the problem the project addresses, the value it creates, and why that value may matter to the specific funder being approached.

6.2.4 Recommended actions

1	Assess ethical alignment before outreach	Define non-negotiables: which sectors, funders, data arrangements, visibility claims, and partnership conditions would be unacceptable. Screen potential partners for risks such as greenwashing, citizen-science-washing, reputational laundering, loss of scientific independence, and damage to participant trust. Set these boundaries before funding pressure rises.
2	Define the private funding landscape precisely	Distinguish between private foundations, philanthropic organisations, corporate foundations, CSR and ESG programmes, industry collaborations, corporate volunteering schemes, benefit corporations, and mission-aligned commercial partners. They have different motivations and require different approaches.
3	Build a targeted value proposition around the partner’s needs	A strong private funding pitch explains what the private actor can achieve through collaboration with the project. CS can offer data, community engagement, environmental insight, employee activation, innovation opportunities, local legitimacy, or educational value. This frames CS as a service or shared-value activity rather than a request for charity. Austin and Reficco (2009) call this “double value creation”: the most durable partnerships are those where both financial and social value are generated simultaneously.
4	Identify the right entry point inside the organisation.	Different organisations engage through different internal routes: CSR teams, ESG departments, sustainability officers, innovation leads, employee engagement managers, or business units with a direct operational interest. Austin and Reficco (2009) highlight the role of corporate social intrapreneurs, internal champions who advance social value creation. CS projects should look to identify and cultivate these internal advocates rather than approaching corporate funders only through formal procurement.
5	Demonstrate impact before scaling outreach	Private funders usually need visible social, environmental, economic, or operational value. Establish clear metrics before expanding private fundraising.
6	Distinguish between CSR partnerships and core-business partnerships	CSR-based partnerships can be useful but may be vulnerable to changing communications priorities. Core-business partnerships may be more durable when the company has a direct operational interest in the data, methods, or environmental issue addressed by the project.

<p style="text-align: center; font-size: 24px; border: 1px solid white; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center; margin: 0 auto;">7</p> <p style="margin-top: 10px;">Consider the “open data plus paid services” model</p>	<p>CS projects do not need to make core data or tools proprietary. A more compatible approach is to keep core data, methods, and tools open, while charging for additional services: analysis, reporting, training, custom tools, consultancy, guided participation, or tailored implementation support.</p>
<p style="text-align: center; font-size: 24px; border: 1px solid white; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center; margin: 0 auto;">8</p> <p style="margin-top: 10px;">Treat corporate volunteering as a potential paid service.</p>	<p>Mature CS platforms or projects that can absorb large numbers of participants may charge companies for curated project lists, guided volunteering activities, training materials, team-based challenges, or impact reports. Only pursue this where coordination capacity exists.</p>
<p style="text-align: center; font-size: 24px; border: 1px solid white; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center; margin: 0 auto;">9</p> <p style="margin-top: 10px;">Establish data governance safeguards</p>	<p>As citizen-generated data becomes valuable for AI, spatial modelling, and commercial analytics, private partnerships should include transparency about data use, participant agency, benefit-sharing, and safeguards against commercial capture. A simple “who benefits?” test applies: support should be treated cautiously where private actors profit from volunteer-generated data without clear public benefit (AAPS, CAPS 2026).</p>

6.2.5 Common risks and trade-offs

If a project accepts support from poorly aligned funders, softens its standards for reputational reasons, or starts talking like a service provider without maintaining scientific and ethical control, it can lose trust quickly. Private partnerships also create greenwashing risks when a funder supports visible participation activities but does not act on the evidence generated. Projects should assess whether the private partner is acting on the evidence and whether continued association strengthens or damages trust.

6.2.6 What to do when things go wrong

If a private partnership becomes ethically compromised or reputationally damaging, the project should have pre-agreed exit terms. Document the decision and communicate it transparently to participants and stakeholders.

6.2.7 Insight from the literature

The social entrepreneurship literature provides useful framing for private partnerships. Alter (2007) maps a spectrum of organisational forms between the purely philanthropic and the purely commercial, a useful reminder that a CS project does not face a binary choice between grant-dependent nonprofit and revenue-driven business; most sustainable positions lie

somewhere in between. Mendell (2010) distinguishes between Anglo-American and European social enterprise models, noting that the European model supports hybrid organisations that combine social goals with revenue generation while relying on public co-funding and civil society networks. CS projects operating in the EU context do not need to choose between public mission and financial sustainability; they can operate within an ecosystem that values both, provided they articulate their social contribution clearly. However, Mendell cautions that social enterprises risk prioritising commercialisation over social impact if they are not anchored in local, government-supported development strategies. For CS, the pursuit of financial sustainability should not lead projects to drift from their core scientific and civic mission.

Battilana et al. (2012), analysing over 3,500 fellowship applications, identify recurring challenges for hybrid organisations: difficulty finding a clear legal framework, the risk of mission drift under financial pressure, challenges in accessing funding that fits neither pure nonprofit grants nor for-profit investment, and cultural difficulty maintaining unified identity across commercial and social objectives. For CS, this translates into the importance of protecting scientific independence and participant-centred values even as the project develops commercially oriented activities. The risk is not commercialisation per se, but commercialisation without adequate governance.

6.2.8 Commercialisation and ethics: a note

Two points from the CROPS roundtables should inform any move toward private or revenue-generating funding.

The roundtables surfaced a broader cultural issue within the CS field: **persistent discomfort around commercialisation**. Some experts argued that this discomfort, while understandable, can itself become a practical barrier to sustainability when it leads projects to reject all private or revenue-generating options without distinguishing between ethically acceptable and problematic forms of commercial activity.

There is a need for more deliberate discussion within the CS community about the conditions under which commercial or hybrid approaches remain compatible with CS principles. Available case evidence does not yet support simple, generalised claims of direct financial return from citizen science. The stronger economic argument is indirect and conditional: CS can generate innovation capacity, service development, trusted datasets, public legitimacy, institutional learning, and market positioning (Schürz et al., 2026). Projects should specify which type of economic value they create, for whom, and under what governance conditions.

Private funding remains both attractive and contentious. It offers flexibility, speed, and the potential to support activities that public grants do not easily cover. It also raises legitimate questions about ethics, independence, community trust, and mission drift. Private funding should be assessed not only by the source of money but by the behaviour it enables. A

partnership that funds participation while avoiding operational change can undermine the credibility of the CS project, even if the activities themselves are well delivered.

A key roundtable insight is that not all private funding is structurally the same. There is an important difference between discretionary CSR or ESG funding and partnerships rooted in a company's core business. The former may be easier to approach but more vulnerable to strategic shifts. The latter may offer greater continuity but require more careful negotiation regarding roles, value exchange, and ethics.

6.2.8.1 Current evidence limitations

Private and industry engagement was the most difficult area to cover in our CROPS data collection activities. Three limits are worth stating plainly.

- The documented cases of sustained, core-business partnerships in citizen science are few. Most private support in the evidence is discretionary CSR or ESG funding, which is easier to approach but more exposed to a company's strategic shifts (CROPS roundtables, 2026).
- The economic argument for CS is mostly indirect: innovation capacity, trusted data, legitimacy, institutional learning. The available evidence does not yet support simple claims of direct financial return (Schürz et al., 2026).
- The field has no shared standards for what makes a commercial partnership ethically acceptable, which is why the guidance here leans on case-by-case assessment rather than a checklist.

Our practical advice is, thus, not to avoid private funding, but to approach it with partnership logic (instead of donation logic), to write the value exchange and the ethical boundaries down before money changes hands. We expect future analysis can update this guidance, as the evidence base grows.

From the field: Reframing citizen science as a service to companies.

OutBe, a benefit corporation, works with private companies to design CS activities for employees and stakeholders. A representative challenged the default approach: "Why are you 'donating' and you're not 'investing'?" Their method starts from the company's needs. In one case, an energy company wanted to bring employees outdoors and contribute to research. OutBe organised monthly bioblitzes using iNaturalist, with employees ranked by species identified. In another, a road construction company funded citizen-led monitoring linked to their infrastructure and climate concerns.

"We tend to go to private companies thinking, 'sorry, I'm stealing your time. Can I ask a favour?' Instead, citizen science could be a service itself. What is the company in need of that citizen science could help them with?"

The lesson: private funding requires a mindset shift from charity to partnership. Projects that articulate what the company gains are far more likely to secure sustained support.

(Source: Expert interviews, May 2026)

◀◀ AT GLANCE: Private Funding

- Best for: mature projects with a clear external value proposition, applied environmental or health initiatives, technology-enabled CS.
- Key preparation: define ethical boundaries, identify the right entry points, build a value proposition around what the funder gains.
- Main risk: mission drift, greenwashing, loss of scientific independence.
- Bottom line: private funding can be valuable, but only when projects are specific, selective, and ethically disciplined.

Go further...

- **Austin and Reficco (2009), Corporate social entrepreneurship:** the full working paper on double value creation. Harvard Business School Working Paper No. 09-101.
- **Battilana et al. (2012), In search of the hybrid ideal:** analysis of hybrid organisations and mission drift. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*.
- **Schürz et al. (2026), Beyond Participation:** ECS case studies of CS organisations with operational private partnerships.
- **CROPS D3.3, Section 2.3** (Moreira et al., 2026): guidance on engaging industry and SMEs, including realistic opportunities and honest limitations.

6.3 Crowdfunding

6.3.1 What practitioners say

“It can never be the only way of funding. It can be part of other things you’re doing if you already have a community, but I wouldn’t recommend it for starting a project.” (Expert group validation discussions, April 2026)

“Crowdfunding works better for projects that have something tangible to give, a tool, a sensor kit. And there are platforms, like Goteo in Spain, that match what you raise with public funds from municipalities.” (Expert group validation discussions, April 2026)

“The reward is the science itself. Backers really appreciate having that open line of discussion with the researchers, and it just normalises that science isn’t linear.” (Expert interviews, May 2026)

6.3.2 When this model fits

Crowdfunding fits best where a project already has a visible support base, a clear public-facing identity, and communications capacity strong enough to sustain a campaign. It is better suited to grassroots or smaller community-led initiatives than to large organisations with slow procurement and branding constraints. It can also work for pilot projects, community-embedded initiatives, or campaigns centred on a tangible item (kit, sensor, educational box). It is much less suitable as the main funding route for core staffing or large operational budgets.

CROPS Validation Workshops indicated that hardware-dependent CS projects face a specific bottom-up funding barrier: local groups may lack the smaller amounts needed to buy kits, sensors, or platform access. FreshWater Watch illustrates this problem, where local groups may need approximately EUR 5,000 to EUR 10,000 for water-testing kits and platform fees.

6.3.3 What needs to be in place first

Before considering crowdfunding, a project needs an existing supporter base, a realistic sense of what those supporters might contribute, and the ability to communicate repeatedly and well. It also needs to confront the ethics of the campaign early: who is being asked to pay, what they are being asked to pay for, and whether it is fair to ask volunteers to finance work they already support with time and labour.

Confirm the administrative and financial route before launch. Check who is legally allowed to receive the funds, which account the platform will pay into, whether funds can be transferred to the project or host organisation, and whether institutional rules on procurement, tax, VAT, or production apply. Resolve this before the campaign goes live.

6.3.4 Recommended actions

1	Start with a cost-benefit judgement, including a true cost-per-euro estimate	Crowdfunding should not be launched just because it seems accessible. Ask whether the likely financial return justifies the time, labour, fulfilment work, and reputational exposure involved. In many cases, the main value is engagement and visibility rather than net income.
2	Assess and cultivate the support base before setting the target	The ask must be proportionate to the community already in place. Think about who is likely to contribute, how much they might reasonably give, and how to build the support base deliberately before the campaign.
3	Choose the platform based on the logic of the campaign	Compare one-off campaign platforms and recurring supporter models, and look at civic crowdfunding options with public match-funding. Match-funding mechanisms can strengthen community campaigns: public donations function as evidence of community interest and as a trigger for additional funding.
4	Co-construct the campaign where possible.	Involve the support network early in shaping what the campaign offers, what seems fair, and what kind of recognition contributors value.
5	Build the story around clear value	The campaign needs a concise explanation of what the project is, why it matters, what the money will unlock, and why it is worth backing now.
6	Seek platform or campaign communications support early	Science-focused platforms often offer communications support: reviewing draft outreach, sharpening the narrative, advising on framing. Projects should seek this before launch, not as a rescue measure mid-campaign.
7	Design rewards carefully and ethically	Tangible rewards often work better than abstract gratitude. On science-focused platforms such as Experiment.com, the science itself is treated as the primary return, with regular lab notes to backers serving as both recognition and accountability.
8	Prepare momentum before launch	Pre-committed supporters, outreach plans, and communications assets need to be in place before the campaign goes live.

<div style="border: 1px solid white; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 0 auto; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;">9</div>	<p>Define what failure looks like before going live</p>	<p>Agree on a threshold for acceptable underperformance and decide in advance what response each scenario warrants: close early, pivot the offer, extend, or shift to personal outreach.</p>
<div style="border: 1px solid white; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 0 auto; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;">10</div>	<p>Develop a structured mid-campaign outreach sequence</p>	<p>Begin with friends and family, move to colleagues and conference contacts, then reach out to professional societies and relevant newsletters. Each stage requires a different kind of ask, drafted and tested in advance.</p>

6.3.5 Common risks and trade-offs

The biggest mistake is treating crowdfunding as a reliable funding mechanism when it is often a demanding engagement mechanism with uncertain financial return. Requests for participant donations require particular care. CS participants already contribute time, data, attention, local knowledge, and unpaid labour. Asking them to give money as well can create ethical tension. Voluntary donations may still be relevant for large platforms if designed carefully: optional, non-disruptive, clearly linked to sustaining shared infrastructure, and never a condition for participation.

From the field: “We are very hesitant to ask participants to donate, because they are already the ones making the research possible.” (Expert interviews, May 2026)

6.3.6 What to do when things go wrong

If a crowdfunding campaign underperforms, apply the pre-agreed threshold. Options include: extending the timeline, revising the ask or rewards, narrowing the goal to a more achievable target, or closing early and redirecting energy. A partial campaign is not necessarily a signal that the project lacks support; it may mean the campaign was poorly timed, poorly sized, or launched without enough pre-committed momentum.

6.3.7 Insight from the literature

Mollick (2014), analysing over 48,500 Kickstarter projects, provides several findings directly applicable to CS campaigns. First, most failed projects raise very little while most successful projects succeed only by a modest margin. Campaigns tend to work when they are realistic in their ask and well-matched to an existing support base. Second, backers respond to visible signals of quality and preparedness: campaigns with a video, early updates, and a professional presentation were significantly more likely to succeed. Social network size was a strong predictor of success, confirming that crowdfunding amplifies existing relationships rather

than replacing them. Third, demand validation is not operational readiness: projects that significantly exceeded their targets were also most likely to experience delivery delays.

The non-financial returns deserve equal weight. Evidence from research crowdfunding shows that campaigns help teams launch projects they could not otherwise start and generate outreach and public engagement benefits that persist beyond the campaign itself (Dahlhausen et al., 2016). For CS projects, whose mission already includes public engagement, this double return is part of the case for trying a small campaign even when the financial yield is expected to be modest.

Evidence from Experiment.com illustrates how crowdfunding can serve as a stepping stone. Campaigns that begin with modest targets have in some cases led to substantially larger institutional grants, with the community-funded work serving as tangible proof of concept. In one early Experiment case, researchers working on a prion disease ran an initial crowdfunding campaign that contributed to a longer research trajectory, eventually leading to further grants, awards, and the creation of a research lab at the Broad Institute. The crowdfunding phase was not a funding mechanism in isolation but the first step in a longer process of credibility-building (Sarah Gulliford, Experiment.com, CROPS expert interview, May 2026).

From the field: How crowdfunding built a pipeline to institutional grants

Experiment.com is a science-focused platform where researchers raise funds directly from the public. A representative explained that crowdfunding should not be treated like a grant application: “People treat the crowdfunding component like it’s a grant, where they put it online and people will just come. That never works.” Successful campaigns require continuous communication and structured outreach. The platform’s most striking insight is the stepping-stone effect. Experiment tracks cases where a modest campaign preceded a much larger grant: one project, for example, began with around USD 8,000 in crowdfunding and later secured roughly USD 800,000 in grant funding. In an early Experiment case, researchers working on a prion disease ran an initial campaign that contributed to a longer trajectory and, in time, the creation of a research lab at the Broad Institute. As the representative put it, “a successful crowdfunding project can go on to get multiple grants, multiple awards, and even start whole research labs.”

On Experiment, the science itself is the reward. “Backers really appreciate having that open line of discussion with the researchers.”

(Source: Expert interviews, May 2026)

AT GLANCE: Crowdfunding

- Best for: grassroots projects, pilot campaigns, tangible kit/sensor funding, community proof-of-concept.

- Key preparation: existing supporter base, realistic target, communications plan, pre-committed momentum.
- Main risk: high effort relative to financial return; ethical tension in asking volunteers to also pay.
- Bottom line: treat crowdfunding as conditional and supplementary, not foundational. It works best where there is already a community and a clear public-facing story.

Go further...

- **Experiment.com** (experiment.com): science-focused crowdfunding platform with communications support for researchers. Operates on an 8% fee model.
 - **Goteo** (goteo.org): civic crowdfunding platform with public match-funding mechanisms from municipalities. Operated by the Platoniq Foundation.
 - **Mollick (2014), The dynamics of crowdfunding**: the empirical study of over 48,500 campaigns. *Journal of Business Venturing*.
 - **Sauermann, Franzoni and Shafi (2019), Crowdfunding scientific research**: correlates of success in science crowdfunding. *PLoS ONE*.
-

6.4 Hybrid funding

6.4.1 What practitioners say

“Mixing public and private, small grants and large grants, gives you more flexibility to manage risk. If you only have national funds and then the political landscape changes, you have nothing in your hands.” (Expert group validation discussions, April 2026)

“It gives you sustainability, but it is a lot of work. You have to switch language, attitude, way of looking, and timing as you move between a public fund, a private fund, and crowdfunding.” (Expert group validation discussions, April 2026)

A representative from Experiment.com compared sustainable funding to an investment strategy: relying on a single source is risky, whereas a diversified, multi-tiered approach improves resilience. (Expert group validation discussions, May 2026)

6.4.2 When this model fits

Hybrid funding fits best for mature organisations, long-term initiatives, infrastructure-heavy platforms, or projects with enough coordination capacity to manage multiple relationships at once. It is often the most realistic model for organisations that cannot survive on grants alone. ECS case studies (Schürz et al., 2026) suggest that hybrid funding is often the main route to continuity: public grants provide legitimacy and initial infrastructure, while longer-term sustainability is built by layering consultancy, paid services, data services, digital infrastructure, subscriptions, corporate partnerships, or institutional support around a public-interest core.

CROPS Validation Workshops found that for mature initiatives with stable communities, applied relevance, and clear governance, transition into a Living Lab model may provide one route toward diversified funding. This is an option for suitable mature projects, not a universal pathway.

6.4.3 What needs to be in place first

A project needs a clear mission, enough internal discipline not to chase every opportunity, and a shared understanding of what success looks like. It also needs relationship capacity: trust-building, partner communication, and expectation management are part of the model itself. Projects should clarify compliance issues early, especially around double-funding and the separation of costs across streams.

Hybrid funding requires permanent capacity for business development, funder communication, partnership management, and strategic decision-making. Without this, hybridisation becomes constant reactive fundraising rather than a sustainability strategy.

6.4.4 Recommended actions

1	Build the hybrid model around a coherent project core	A hybrid model fails when it becomes a series of separate pitches to different audiences. Scientific purpose should remain visible alongside social, environmental, economic, and strategic value. Define the full impact profile early, showing how the same work generates value across multiple domains. Public funders should receive proposals foregrounding scientific and governance outcomes. Private funders should receive pitches foregrounding societal and economic outcomes. Community audiences should receive campaigns foregrounding environmental and social value. The language can change, but the project should not become something different every time it speaks.
2	Build metrics early and protect them from funding drift	Projects need a monitoring framework that tracks social, scientific, environmental, and financial value and does not get rewritten every time a new funder appears.
3	Assign explicit ownership of each funding relationship	Every major relationship should have a named owner responsible for maintaining contact, tracking expectations, coordinating reporting, and identifying follow-up opportunities.
4	Schedule a periodic funding audit	At least once a year, map each funding source, its conditions, its administrative burden, its strategic value, and its alignment with the project’s mission. Ask: which streams support the mission? Which ones are distorting priorities? Which require too much work for too little strategic value?
5	Use a stable base-load source where possible	Anchor the hybrid strategy around one relatively stable, multi-year source and layer additional streams around it. Without that base, hybrid funding can become constant, reactive fundraising with little operational stability.
6	Manage expectations explicitly	Different funding streams require different writing, timing, accountability, and relationship strategies. Explain timelines, research uncertainty, likely outputs, and practical limits to each partner.
7	Identify conflicts of interest and practical constraints	Hybrid partnerships can fail over strategic conflicts, evidence expectations, communications rules, data access, or reputational risk. Diversification is useful only if it supports the mission.

8

before accepting funding.

Resource the operational burden of hybrid funding

Managing different languages, timelines, accountability formats, and relationship practices is real work. Budget coordination capacity as part of the funding strategy.

6.4.5 Business models relevant to CS

Social entrepreneurship helps CS projects think about operating models, not only funding sources. The models below are drawn from the CROPS evidence and literature, and become more or less realistic depending on the project’s maturity, data quality, community base, and institutional relationships.

Table 6.1. Business models relevant to CS funding and sustainability

Model	What stays open	What generates revenue	Main condition or risk
Open data plus paid services	Core datasets, metadata, documentation	Tailored analysis, reports, dashboards, policy briefs, workshops	Revenue must not create exclusive access to citizen-generated data
Data quality and certification	Raw data, methods, transparent quality notes	Validation, QA reports, certified data feeds, methodology audits	Credible only when data limitations are explicit
Open-source platform plus hosted services	Source code, documentation, standard tools	Managed hosting, maintenance, custom deployment, support	Requires governance that protects the open core from client capture
Knowledge brokerage	Generic methods, public learning resources	Training, consultancy, participation design, impact-measurement support	Service work must not displace research or community commitments
Co-production cost model	Public-interest outputs, participation methods	Public funding justified by cost-efficiency compared with professional-only monitoring	Credible only with validated data; CS should not be framed as cheap labour

Federated commons / infrastructure membership	Shared standards, core tools, datasets	public institutional contributions, governance contributions	Membership fees, co-contributions	Requires mass and safeguards against capture	critical mass and governance
--	--	--	-----------------------------------	--	------------------------------

Source: CROPS expert interviews, validation workshops, and synthesis of Mitra et al. (2020), François and Goi (2023), and Schürz et al. (2026).

These models can be combined, but openness should be treated as a governance commitment rather than as the thing being sold. Sequencing matters: early-stage projects usually need to prove data quality and delivery capacity first; established projects can test services; mature projects may sustain shared infrastructure if governance protects the mission.

6.4.6 Common risks and trade-offs

Hybrid funding can become exhausting, reactive, and strategically incoherent. The risks include mission drift, weak metrics, unmanaged partner expectations, and organisational overload. The more hybrid the model becomes, the more deliberate the coordination has to be. The core risk is losing the distinction between what defines the initiative, what funders will pay for, and what can generate revenue.

6.4.7 What to do when things go wrong

If hybrid funding becomes incoherent or exhausting, conduct the annual funding audit described above. Be prepared to drop a funding stream that costs more in coordination, mission distortion, or team burnout than it contributes in strategic value. Simplifying a hybrid model is sometimes the strongest sustainability decision.

6.4.8 Insight from the literature

Battilana et al. (2012) argue that hybrid organisations have strong potential to scale impact, but only if the tensions between social and commercial objectives are actively managed through deliberate governance structures, explicit cultural values, and ongoing monitoring of the balance between mission and market. Foster, Kim and Christiansen (2009) complement this insight: the most sustainable funding models are those where the sources of funds, the types of decision-makers authorising those funds, and the motivations of those decision-makers are understood clearly and consistently. Building a hybrid model should be a deliberate strategy to engage multiple, stable funder communities in ways appropriate to what the project delivers, not an ad hoc response to funding gaps.

Mitra et al. (2020) provide conceptual grounding through the concept of citizen entrepreneurship, which reconceives citizens as active participants in the production, governance, and innovation of the services and knowledge they use. This framing supports

community-based and civic funding models by presenting citizen participation as a form of collective value creation that communities have a stake in sustaining.

6.4.9 Sustainability lessons from CROPS case studies

The CROPS Validation Workshops and expert interviews documented practical sustainability mechanisms and risks across several European CS initiatives.

Table 6.2. Sustainability lessons from CROPS case-study projects

CS Project focus	Sustainability lesson
Plastic pollution	Large hidden communication and validation labour: the core team exchanged over 11,000 emails to chase missing data and verify photos from schools. This effort is rarely funded.
Marine observation	Complex multi-project platforms can become financially dependent on external IT maintenance. With 16 sub-projects and no in-house developer, IT is a major drain.
Soil pollution	Apps built during Horizon projects can fall into a post-grant hosting and coordination gap once funding ends.
Seed sharing	Small annual B2B/B2G fees (public libraries pay for a shared digital app) can support app maintenance across 22 locations. However, fee-based access may conflict with openness goals.
Decomposition	“Piggybacking” on existing monitoring networks (FAO, LTER, SoilBON) reduces infrastructure costs.
Mapping	Scaling through trusted open infrastructure (OpenStreetMap) avoids the cost of building a new network.
Water quality	Local kit and platform costs (~EUR 5,000-10,000 per group) can block bottom-up scaling even when the central platform exists.

Source: Expert interviews and Expert group validation discussions (2025-2026).

6.4.10 Economic value creation in practice

The ECS Impact Book (Schürz et al., 2026) documents how CS organisations translate participation into economic value through different business models.

Table 6.3. CS organisations generating economic value (selected ECS examples)

Organisation	Model in practice	Revenue mechanism
--------------	-------------------	-------------------

MMOS	Gaming industry integration	Companies pay for embedding scientific tasks into commercial games
Anè·lides	Blue education and eco-tourism	Public grants combined with paid educational and tourism services
SPOTTERON	Digital participation infrastructure	Commercial CS app development and hosting for research institutions
PULSAQUA	Water-monitoring services	Public grants, NGO partnerships, training courses, monitoring contracts
DigVentures	Participatory heritage	Revenue from archaeological fieldwork participation and corporate engagement
STAB VIDA	Biotechnology validation	Citizen participation for real-world product validation

Source: Schürz et al. (2026), *Beyond Participation*.

From the field: How Zooniverse built a hybrid model

Zooniverse is the world’s largest platform for people-powered research, hosting hundreds of CS projects across disciplines. Its funding has evolved through deliberate layering: research grants (primarily US and UK research councils), institutional support from the University of Oxford and the Adler Planetarium, and paid corporate volunteering services.

A representative explained that the platform remains free for researchers and volunteers. Revenue from corporate volunteering comes from offering companies curated project lists, guided volunteering sessions, team-based challenges, and impact reports. This works because Zooniverse already has the scale to absorb additional participants without distorting the science.

Two principles underpin the model. First, “investing in shared infrastructure is key; otherwise, projects keep building disconnected tools that then become long-term maintenance costs.” Zooniverse invests in reusable infrastructure serving many projects rather than building bespoke tools for each. Second, the team is “very hesitant to ask participants to donate, because they are already the ones making the research possible.” Voluntary donation options exist but are optional, non-disruptive, and framed as supporting shared infrastructure.

The key lesson: each funding stream has its own coherent logic, the core infrastructure is shared, and the team resisted commercialising what participants already provide for free.

(Source: Expert interviews, May 2026)

◀◀ AT GLANCE: Hybrid Funding

- Best for: mature organisations, long-term initiatives, infrastructure-heavy platforms.
- Key preparation: coherent core mission, stable base-load source, governance capacity, relationship management.
- Main risk: mission drift, coordination overload, becoming funding-led.
- Bottom line: hybrid funding is often necessary, but the smartest hybrid model is not the most complex one; it is the simplest one that still reduces dependency and preserves strategic coherence.

Go further...

- **Foster, Kim and Christiansen (2009), Ten nonprofit funding models:** the foundational typology for mission-driven organisations. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*.
- **François and Goi (2023), Business model for scaling social impact:** analysis of business models for social entrepreneurs. *Sustainability*.
- **Mitra et al. (2020), Citizen entrepreneurship:** the conceptual framework for citizens as participants in value creation and governance. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Emerging Economies*.

6.5 Transition planning: moving between models

Each of the four funding models can function as a starting point, a stepping stone, or a long-term strategy depending on the project's stage and context. Most CS projects that achieve financial sustainability do so not by perfecting one model but by moving between models at the right time and in the right sequence. Transition points are often where otherwise strong projects fail.

Transition planning should begin before the original funding ends. Projects should identify which functions must continue, which can be reduced, which could be paid for by external stakeholders, and which should remain free for participants.

Warning. Projects with apps, databases, dashboards, or digital platforms should plan specifically for the post-grant IT trap: tools built during a funded project may lose hosting, updates, user support, and active coordination once the grant ends. Transition planning should identify who will pay for hosting, maintenance, data security, bug fixes, documentation, and user support after the project period (CROPS Validation Workshops, 2026).

6.5.1 From crowdfunding or cascading grants to competitive public funding

A successful crowdfunding campaign or a completed FSTP grant can function as proof of concept for a public funding application. Projects making this transition should document outcomes carefully, formalise their scientific rationale, and begin network-building well before the application window opens. The standards and language of competitive public funding are substantially different from what worked at the community stage.

From the field: Experiment.com tracks cases where a small campaign preceded a much larger grant: one project began with around USD 8,000 in crowdfunding and went on to secure roughly USD 800,000 in grant funding. As a representative put it, “a successful crowdfunding project can go on to get multiple grants, multiple awards, and even start whole research labs.” (Expert interviews, May 2026)
Build the transition case during the campaign, not after it. Open documentation of progress (lab notes, campaign updates, preliminary outputs, published results) serves as evidence for funders reviewing a later grant application.

6.5.2 From single-source public funding to a first private partnership

When a project has one public grant as its main income, adding a private partner can strengthen resilience and extend reach. But the first private partnership is the hardest to manage well, because norms and expectations have not been established. Treat this

transition as a learning process, start with a clearly bounded collaboration, and document what worked.

6.5.3 From single-stream to hybrid

This transition carries the highest operational risk. Projects should resist adding new funding streams reactively. A more sustainable approach is to add one new stream at a time, stabilise it, assess the coordination cost, and only then consider adding another.

6.5.4 From researcher-led project to mixed-capacity team

CS projects that begin inside research institutions may have strong scientific expertise but limited capacity for communication, marketing, community management, business development, or service design. This can become a sustainability barrier. Projects seeking long-term sustainability may need to bring in communication specialists, community managers, partnership leads, or external service-design expertise.

6.5.5 From project survival to continuity beyond the original organisation

Sustainability may mean training others, documenting processes, creating redundancy, becoming or finding a fiscal sponsor, merging, or moving the work into a new institutional home. Transition planning should include a scale/refocus/stop decision: which activities truly need to continue, which can be reduced, which should be transferred, and which can responsibly end.

From the field: “It’s not just science, it’s also community, and so we cannot only live off what science lives off.” (OutBe, Expert interview, May 2026)

See also CROPS D3.1, *Protocols for Upscaling* (Fraisl et al., 2026), which provides persona-based scaling protocols for CS projects at different stages and in different scaling directions, including dedicated sections on financial and structural sustainability for each scaling pathway.

7 Step 6: Build the Foundations and Sustain

Choosing a model is not the end of the work. Whatever route a project takes, the same operational foundations decide whether funding can be won, managed, and renewed: knowing what is available, being able to evidence value to funders, governing data and AI responsibly, and paying for the systems that keep participation credible even when they are invisible in a budget.

7.1 Building funding intelligence and visibility

Two practical capabilities, drawn consistently from the CROPS expert interviews, underpin every funding strategy regardless of the model chosen.

Funding intelligence. The biggest practical barrier many CS projects face is not knowing what exists. Projects should maintain a living map of funding calls, updated with multiple search terms and covering non-research instruments at every scale. Monitoring calls, understanding procurement rules, cultivating funder relationships, and knowing which partners can carry grant administration require dedicated time; they should not be treated as spare-time tasks on top of fieldwork, platform maintenance, and volunteer coordination (AAPS, CAPS 2026).

Projects should build internal peer-learning practices that distinguish supportive funders from funders whose reporting and compliance requirements undermine mission-based work. CS networks can help by sharing practical intelligence on funder practices and by redirecting unsuitable opportunities to better-fitted organisations rather than treating all funding as a zero-sum competition.

Visibility through knowledge sharing. Running workshops, publishing how-to guides, and presenting at events not only builds the CS field; it keeps organisations visible to potential funders, partners, and consortium members. This is how teams stay fundable between grants: by being known, credible, and already in conversation with the people who matter before calls open.

A directory of platforms for networking, visibility and funding intelligence is provided in Annex H.

7.2 Linking evaluation design to funder communication

Kieslinger et al. (2018) propose an open evaluation framework for CS that organises assessment across three dimensions: scientific quality, participant outcomes, and socio-ecological and economic effects. This framework is useful for CS projects not only for evaluation but as a communication tool for funders. Projects that can show clear scientific goals, evidence of participant development, and measurable community or environmental effects are better positioned to make the case for sustained funding.

A key insight from Kieslinger et al. is that evaluation should begin at the planning stage, not after implementation. Projects that build monitoring into their design from the outset generate more credible evidence and avoid the common trap of conflating outputs with impacts. Wehn et al. (2021) make a complementary point: CS projects often treat outputs (data collected), outcomes (increased awareness), and impacts (shifts in governance or ecosystem management) as if they were the same thing. This blurring weakens impact claims and makes it harder to justify sustained funding.

For funding communication, the project’s monitoring framework should be visibly integrated into proposals and partnership agreements, not treated as a back-office reporting function. Established tools such as MICS (Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science) and SROI (Social Return on Investment) provide structured frameworks for demonstrating value. Templates for both are included in Annex D.

From the field: The COESO policy brief on funding CS in the social sciences and humanities explicitly recommends that funders assess “not only the results, but also the quality of the cooperation that actually takes place” (Smaniotto, 2022). Funder interview data from the same programme confirmed that weak assessment of participation quality is among the most common reasons follow-on funding is not renewed. For CS projects, the depth, inclusivity, and governance of the co-production relationship is a fundable claim that should be evidenced and reported alongside scientific and social outcomes.

7.3 Communicating with different funders

Different funders respond to different languages, formats, timelines, and value framings.

Table 7.1. Communication approaches by funder type

Funder type		What they want to hear		Format and style		Relationship
Public/EU evaluators	grant	Scientific methodology, relevance, metrics	rationale, policy impact	Formal following criteria; budget	proposal call detailed	Application-driven; feedback via evaluation reports
National councils	research	Scientific national open alignment	quality, relevance, science	Formal but shorter; include stage	often may interview	May require prior contact with programme officers

Private foundations	Social environmental impact, reach, alignment	or community thematic	Narrative-driven proposals or letters of interest	Relationship-led; programme officer is key
Corporate CSR / ESG	Employee engagement, sustainability reporting, community legitimacy	visibility, community	Brief partnership pitch; corporate language	Find the internal champion; start with an exploratory conversation
Corporate business core-	Operational data, innovation, positioning	value: intelligence, market	Service proposal; CS framed as a business input	Longer cycle; understand the partner's needs
Crowdfunding backers	Tangible problem, personal connection, clear use of funds, transparency	problem, connection, use of funds,	Short video, clear campaign page, regular lab notes	Community-driven; pre-launch cultivation essential
Institutional funders	Cost-efficiency, institutional relevance, strategic contribution	strategic	Internal proposal or business case	Internal advocacy; demonstrate demand first

From the field: “The main thing that is missing is communication guidelines, something that is done by real communication experts. Projects need to work with third parties to better communicate their projects.” (Expert interviews, May 2026)

Adapting the pitch to each funder has limits.

CS initiatives can benefit from positioning flexibility: a platform or project may be framed as research infrastructure, public engagement, education, AI training, environmental monitoring, social innovation, or open science, depending on the funder. This can open doors, but it can also create confusion if the project appears too educational for research funders, too research-focused for education funders, or too infrastructural for project-based calls.

The strategic challenge is to adapt the language for different funders without losing a coherent core identity. Funding narratives can change, but the project should not become a different project every time it speaks to a different funder.

See also CROPS D3.3 (Moreira et al., 2026), Section 2.5 (Communicate and Build Trust), for communication approaches by stakeholder group.

7.4 Cross-cutting considerations: AI, data governance and ethics

Three cross-cutting themes affect funding strategy across all four funding categories.

AI and citizen science. AI is increasingly integrated into CS, from automated species identification and image classification to data quality assurance and real-time participant coaching (Fraisl et al., 2025; Fortson et al., 2024). This has funding implications across the board. Public funders increasingly expect projects to demonstrate how AI supports (rather than replaces) citizen participation. Private funders and industry partners may see citizen-generated data as a training resource for AI systems, raising questions about data ownership, participant consent, and benefit-sharing. For projects seeking to reduce unsustainable manual validation costs, semi-automated QA/QC can be a legitimate budget line, but AI tools should be transparent, validated, monitored for bias, and paired with expert review (CROPS Validation Workshops, 2026).

Lotfian et al. (2026) propose a framework for responsible AI integration in CS grounded in four pillars: developing standards and ethical and legal frameworks; promoting digital inclusivity and reducing the digital divide; balancing technology with human capacity; and ensuring environmental sustainability. In practical terms, projects should develop a data stewardship plan that informs participants in advance about how their data may be used for AI training, and adopt good practice around anonymity (Ceccaroni et al., 2019), alongside broader privacy and consent safeguards (Bowser et al., 2020).

Data governance across funding types. As citizen-generated data becomes valuable for spatial modelling, commercial analytics, environmental intelligence, and policy monitoring, CS projects need clear governance frameworks regardless of the funding source. This includes: who owns the data; who can access it and under what conditions; how participant consent is managed; whether data can be used commercially; and what safeguards exist against extraction of citizen-generated outputs without public benefit. These questions are especially pressing when private funding is involved, but they also arise with public funders who require open data policies, and with hybrid models where data flows across multiple partners.

Ethical safeguards. CS projects must take into account ethical considerations including participant privacy, GDPR compliance, the ECSA 10 Principles of Citizen Science, and responsible research and innovation (RRI) commitments. Ethical boundaries should be defined before funding pressure rises, because projects are more likely to compromise when they are already financially vulnerable. The Ethics and CS Principles Checklist in Annex D supports this assessment.

7.5 Funding the invisible systems

The discussion of sustainability should not be limited to asking where money comes from. It should also address organisational capacity, workload, governance, skills, and the practical ability to maintain activities over time.

Traditional research systems tend to reward outputs, publications, and project novelty more than relationship maintenance, participation quality, infrastructure reuse, and community-defined outcomes. This affects funding by making the actual conditions of participatory science less visible in evaluation criteria. The CAPS 2026 plenary warned that volunteer-enabled science is not free: if projects survive funding gaps through unpaid labour and improvised coordination, funders may wrongly conclude that sustained support is unnecessary (AAPS, 2026).

CROPS Validation Workshops show that sustainability failures often arise when projects fund visible activities but not the invisible systems that make them credible: communication with participants, IT maintenance, quality assurance, legal hosting, local kit access, and data stewardship. These should be treated as core sustainability infrastructure. In citizen science projects, this “invisible infrastructure” is especially important because credibility depends not only on data collection, but on sustained participation, volunteer support, training, data validation, feedback, and stewardship. Some guidance does exist for making these costs more explicit. For example, UKEOF’s work on citizen science and environmental monitoring includes a framework for assessing costs, benefits, and opportunities, including both financial and non-monetised costs. Its data management guidance also asks projects to plan across the full data lifecycle, from collection and storage through publication and reuse. The US EPA’s participatory science quality assurance toolkit similarly treats quality assurance, transparent methods, documentation, and project management as core design requirements rather than add-ons. Sector guidance from JNCC also highlights volunteer recruitment, communication, training, risk management, and participant journey design as necessary parts of credible citizen science delivery²³⁴⁵⁶⁷.

The main strategic risk is becoming funding-led: reshaping the project repeatedly to fit available money until it no longer serves its original scientific or civic purpose. Funding diversification should be treated as a managed transition, not an automatic sign of maturity.

² UK Environmental Observation Framework. (n.d.). *Citizen Science Working Group*. Retrieved June 29, 2026, from <https://ukeof.org.uk/our-work/citizen-science>

³ Chapman, C., Pocock, M., Parr, J., Brown, M., Letheren, B., & UKEOF Citizen Science Working Group. (2020). *Data management planning for citizen science*. UK Environmental Observation Framework. <https://ukeof.org.uk/sites/default/files/2023-09/UKEOF-data-guidance-booklet-web.pdf>

⁴ UK Environmental Observation Framework. (n.d.). *Understanding opportunities, cost and benefits of citizen science*. Retrieved June 29, 2026, from <https://ukeof.org.uk/our-work/citizen-science/cswg-outputs/opps-costs-benefits-2016>

⁵ U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. (2026, March 9). *Quality assurance handbook and toolkit for participatory science projects*. <https://www.epa.gov/participatory-science/quality-assurance-handbook-and-toolkit-participatory-science-projects>

⁶ Joint Nature Conservation Committee. (2024, January 11). *Monitoring for nature recovery and local change*. <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/citizen-science-for-local-change/>

⁷ Joint Nature Conservation Committee. (2024, January 11). *Monitoring for nature recovery and local change: Survey methods and tools*. <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/citizen-science-survey-methods-and-tools/>

The core risk is losing the distinction between what defines the initiative, what funders will pay for, and what can generate revenue. Funding strategies should preserve that distinction.

STEP 7 AT GLANCE: Build the Foundations and Sustain

- Treat funding intelligence and visibility as an ongoing operational role, not a spare-time task.
- Design evaluation into the project from the start and use it as a funder-communication tool.
- Address AI, data governance, and ethics proactively across every funding type, not only where private money is involved.
- Budget for the invisible systems (coordination, IT, data validation, community support, hosting). They are the infrastructure that makes participation credible, and they are where sustainability most often fails.
-

Go further...

- **CROPS D3.3, Guidelines for Stakeholder Engagement** (Moreira et al., 2026): the step-by-step guide to engaging stakeholders across the quadruple helix. Especially relevant for building the funder relationships and consortium partnerships described in this chapter.
- **Kieslinger et al. (2018), The challenge of evaluation**: the open evaluation framework drawn on in Section 7.2. In Hecker et al. (Eds.), *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*, UCL Press.
- **ECSA 10 Principles of Citizen Science**: the widely adopted principles for ethical CS practice. Available at: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/10-principles/>
- **Lotfian et al. (2026), A vision for responsible AI integration in citizen science**: the four-pillar framework for responsible AI in CS. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-026-06594-5>
- **Ceccaroni et al. (2019), Opportunities and risks for citizen science in the age of artificial intelligence**: early, practical recommendations on data stewardship and anonymity. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.241>
-

8 Recommendations

The project-level recommendations in Steps 1 to 6 show what CS initiatives can do to mobilise funding and strengthen sustainability. Several barriers identified in the analysis, however, require the agency of different actors. These barriers relate to funding architecture, eligibility rules, institutional incentives, shared infrastructure, and the way CS is recognised within research, open science, civic engagement, and community-development systems.

These recommendations are addressed to research councils, ministries, municipalities, universities, foundations, public agencies, and other organisations designing or managing funding instruments for CS. They are organised by audience.

8.1 For funders and funding agencies

- 1. Create dedicated and proportionate CS funding pathways.** Large competitive grants are not always appropriate for small, local, or newly emerging initiatives. Dedicated pathways should include smaller seed grants, cascading funding, extension grants for existing research projects, and longer-term instruments for established initiatives, proportionate in scale, administrative burden, and eligibility requirements. The OECD (2025) identifies the design of effective funding programmes as central to embedding CS into national research systems, alongside the legal and policy environment, institutional research culture, capacity building, supporting infrastructure, and societal dialogue.
- 2. Support shared infrastructure rather than repeatedly funding disconnected tools.** Prioritise shared platforms, repositories, data standards, interoperability tools, training resources, governance frameworks, and long-term maintenance. ECS case studies (Schürz et al., 2026) indicate that reusable infrastructure and service layers are where much of CS's economic value becomes sustainable. Funding should cover maintenance, interoperability, documentation, community management, and service adaptation, so that tools become shared assets rather than one-off outputs.
- 3. Address eligibility barriers for citizen-led initiatives.** Create routes that allow citizen groups, civil society organisations, municipalities, and community partners to access appropriate funding directly or through fair partnership models. Larger institutions should use their administrative capacity to reduce the grant-writing, compliance, and reporting burden on grassroots partners rather than merely inviting them into consortia.
- 4. Develop question-led funding calls.** Support models in which citizen groups or civil society organisations can propose research questions, with researchers joining later to develop the scientific design. This shifts CS from a researcher-led model toward a more participatory one. Funders should design contracts that accommodate iterative participatory scopes of work.

5. **Recognise participation support as a core eligible cost.** Facilitation, community management, volunteer coordination, communication, training, translation, feedback loops, and participant support are core delivery costs, not optional overheads. The hidden administrative burden of scaled data collection (follow-up with schools, verification of submitted data, moderation, technical support) should also be eligible.
6. **Make physical convening and local engagement costs eligible.** Meaningful CS often requires in-person trust-building, workshops, meetings, field activities, and community-based facilitation. For hardware-based projects, small local equipment and access costs (kits, sensors, sample materials, platform fees) should also be eligible.
7. **Fund evaluation and impact measurement from the start.** Require credible monitoring plans but also provide the budget and flexibility to implement them. Evaluation should begin at the planning stage. Evaluation budgets should include proportionate investment in semi-automated QA/QC where it can reduce unsustainable manual validation costs.
8. **Support networks and intermediary organisations that connect projects to funders.** A recurring barrier is not eligibility but discoverability. Fund national and European networks, helpdesks, matchmaking platforms, and intermediary organisations that connect CS projects with appropriate funding opportunities.

8.2 For policymakers and public authorities

1. **Embed CS within open science and institutional funding structures.** CS should be recognised as part of the wider open science agenda, with dedicated budgets, tailored instruments, and clear institutional responsibility, not treated only as an optional outreach component.
2. **Create joint co-funding mechanisms across administrative silos.** CS projects often combine research, public engagement, education, environmental monitoring, community development, and policy relevance. No single funder may be able to support the full scope. Research councils, ministries, municipalities, and foundations should explore joint instruments where each funder supports the component that fits its mandate.
3. **Treat sustainability as an ecosystem responsibility, not only a project responsibility.** Long-term sustainability depends on funders that design appropriate instruments, institutions that embed successful activities, platforms that maintain shared infrastructure, policymakers that recognise CS as part of public knowledge production, and communities that remain meaningfully involved. Funding frameworks should favour recurring budget lines, mandates, embedded procedures, shared infrastructure, and formal partnerships capable of surviving political or staff turnover.

8.3 For host institutions and universities

- 1. Support institutional embedding from the beginning of seed funding.** Require and support projects to plan for continuation beyond the grant period. This does not mean expecting every project to become financially self-sufficient, but it does mean asking how successful activities, infrastructure, partnerships, and expertise could be embedded in host institutions, public services, networks, or communities.
- 2. Recognise methodology transfer as a sustainability outcome.** In CS, sustainability may also mean that methods, tools, practices, datasets, training materials, or participatory approaches are reused by other organisations, embedded in institutions, or adapted in new contexts. Evaluators should recognise this kind of transfer as a valid sustainability outcome.

8.4 For the wider CS ecosystem

- 1. Protect openness, public interest, and scientific independence in funding design.** Funding instruments should include safeguards that protect CS from mission drift, greenwashing, citizen-science-washing, or inappropriate private influence, especially in hybrid and private funding models. Require transparency around data governance, participant rights, publication independence, conflicts of interest, and the role of private partners.
- 2. Encourage multi-funder consortium models for cross-sector CS.** Where CS initiatives sit across several domains, multi-funder models that bring together public, private, philanthropic, and third-sector actors around a shared programme can help overcome the problem that CS is often peripheral to several funding areas but central to none.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable completes the work begun in D4.3, which mapped the CS funding landscape and established the empirical baseline: a field dominated by short-term public grant funding, with persistent sustainability challenges and underused alternative models. D4.5 translates that diagnosis into treatment, a six-step protocol refined from the preliminary version (D4.4) through stakeholder feedback.

The six steps form a single sequence, and it is worth restating it here in full. **Step 1 (Chapter 2)** maps the funding landscape: the four funding families (public, community, private, hybrid), who actually pays and why, and how participation design shapes what can be funded. **Step 2 (Chapter 3)** asks projects to diagnose their own stage, early, established, or mature, and their scaling direction, because the route that suits a grassroots group rarely suits an institutional platform. **Step 3 (Chapter 4)** provides the Funding Fit Framework and its scored self-assessment, a structured test of whether a specific opportunity is worth scarce application capacity. **Step 4 (Chapter 5)** turns the diagnosis into a funding model: an anchor source, complementary sources, and the business-model options for projects ready to generate revenue. **Step 5 (Chapter 6)** is the selection guide itself, the detailed manual for pursuing public, private, crowdfunding, and hybrid routes, and for managing transitions between them. **Step 6 (Chapter 7)** addresses what keeps a funded project alive: the invisible systems, evaluation as funder communication, visibility, and planning beyond the current grant. Chapter 8 then turns from what projects can do to what the system around them must do, and the annexes supply the working tools, from the Funding Readiness Checklist to the business-model setup guidance.

Read as one sequence, the protocol's underlying logic is simple: understand the landscape before acting in it; understand your own position before choosing a route; test fit before committing capacity; build a model rather than chasing single grants; execute the chosen route well; and sustain the systems that make the work credible.

What the evidence showed

The protocol's recommendations rest on a consistent set of findings across the CROPS evidence base, the D4.3 mapping, eighteen expert interviews in two rounds, two roundtables, the ECSA and ENCC workshops, and the validation workshops. Restated briefly, five findings carried the most weight.

First, short-term public grants remain the dominant funding source, and their sustainability potential is low: funding ends with the project, and reapplication consumes capacity continuously. Second, the costs that most often sink projects are the invisible ones, coordination, IT maintenance, data validation, community support, legal hosting, which grants rarely cover and projects rarely budget for. Third, private and industry engagement is the least developed area in the field, held back less by lack of corporate interest than by the

absence of shared ethical standards, service-design capacity, and business development skills on the CS side. Fourth, crowdfunding yields modest sums and works best as a community-building and proof-of-concept instrument rather than a core income source. Fifth, the most sustainable initiatives combine several sources in deliberate hybrid models, but hybridity demands coordination capacity and governance that many projects lack. These findings are developed, with their sources, in Chapters 2 to 7; they are restated here because every recommendation in this protocol traces back to one or more of them.

The practical bottom line for practitioners

For CS practitioners and project coordinators, the findings above translate into five working conclusions, each anchored in a specific step of the protocol.

Know where you stand. The funding landscape is broader than many projects realise, but not all options are equally accessible. Before approaching any funder, apply the Funding Fit Framework and the scored self-assessment (Step 3). If the total falls below 15, the project is probably not yet ready for that particular route. That is not a judgement on its value; it is useful information about where some groundwork is still needed.

Prepare before you pitch. The most common causes of funding failure observed in the evidence are not weak ideas but weak preparation: unclear value propositions, missing evaluation frameworks, unrealistic budgets, or insufficient network-building (Steps 4 and 6).

Match the model to the project, not the other way around. A grassroots project that pursues a coordinated Horizon Europe bid before it is ready can spend months of scarce capacity for little return, when partner roles or cascading (FSTP) calls would fit its stage. A mature platform that relies on crowdfunding alone may be overlooking steadier and more substantial sources. The stage-based readiness framework (Step 2) exists to prevent both errors.

Fund the invisible systems. Coordination, IT maintenance, data validation, community support, legal hosting, and institutional responsibility are not overheads; they are the infrastructure that makes participation credible (Step 6). Plastic Pirates exchanged 11,000 emails to validate school submissions. SoilPlastic faces a post-grant hosting gap. These are not edge cases; they are the norm.

Be honest about what the field has not yet solved. Private and industry engagement remains the weakest area. The CS community still lacks shared standards for evaluating when a commercial partnership is compatible with CS principles and when it is not. Progress requires not only better outreach to private funders but a more candid internal conversation about the conditions under which commercial approaches are acceptable (Step 5; Chapter 8).

For funders and policymakers

Practitioners, however, can only work within the system they are given, and several of the findings in 9.2 point to constraints no individual project can remove. The policy and funder recommendations in Chapter 8 address these structural barriers directly: funding architecture that excludes grassroots initiatives, eligibility rules that require legal infrastructure many citizen-led groups lack, institutional incentives that reward novelty over maintenance, and shared infrastructure that remains chronically underfunded.

The OECD (2025), in its analysis of citizen science in national research policy, reaches a similar conclusion: effective integration depends on action across the whole enabling environment, not on funding instruments alone (the six enabling factors are set out in Chapter 8). Projects can adapt to the system as it exists, but the system itself also needs to change.

Next steps and uptake targets

The protocol will be treated as a living resource. As the CS funding landscape evolves, particularly with the increasing role of AI, new EU funding instruments, and growing private-sector engagement, the evidence base will need updating. CROPS partners will revisit and refine the guidance as new data becomes available, and to share practical experience of applying the protocol with the wider CS community.

Tip: Where to get support. Some of the steps in this protocol, notably proposal preparation for competitive calls (Section 6.1), business-model development (Section 6.4 and Annex C), and impact evidencing for funder communication (Section 7.2), are areas where projects often benefit from working with experienced partners rather than learning everything alone. Projects applying this protocol can contact the CROPS consortium for guidance on its use. INOVA+, the task leader responsible for this protocol, welcomes contact from CS initiatives seeking support in putting the guidance into practice (www.inova.business).

Give your feedback: Feedback from projects using the protocol is also valuable and welcome: ines.francisco@inova.business / tania.moreira@inova.business

* * *

The CS funding problem is not, at its root, a marketing problem. It is a structural problem. Public funding systems were designed for institutions, not communities. Research evaluation criteria reward novelty over maintenance. CS sits between multiple policy domains, research, environment, education, health, civic engagement, and is peripheral to all of them. Private engagement is underdeveloped because the field has not yet built the ethical infrastructure, the service-design capacity, or the business development skills to make it work at scale.

This protocol can help individual projects navigate within these constraints. It cannot fix the constraints themselves. That requires the systemic changes described in Chapter 8: dedicated CS funding pathways, institutional embedding, shared infrastructure investment, longer timescales, and recognition that the systems supporting participation are worth paying for.

The strongest conclusion from this work is also the simplest: citizen science that depends on a single grant and treats coordination, IT, and community support as dispensable will not survive. Citizen science that builds funding strategy into its design from the start, budgets for the invisible systems, and cultivates the relationships needed for long-term support has a real chance.

The protocol is a tool. Whether it works depends on whether the people who read it act on it, and whether the funders and policymakers who shape the system are willing to change it.

10 References

- Alter, K. (2007). *Social Enterprise Typology*. Virtue Ventures. Available at: <https://isfcolombia.uniandes.edu.co/images/201519/LRD31.pdf>
- Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences (AAPS). (2026). CAPS 2026 closing plenary: Funding participation, building sustainable pathways for PS [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OXX0Msl3leo>
- Austin, J. E., & Reficco, E. (2009). Corporate social entrepreneurship (Harvard Business School Working Paper No. 09-101). Harvard Business School.
- Battilana, J., Lee, M., Walker, J., & Dorsey, C. (2012). In search of the hybrid ideal. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, Summer 2012. Available at: https://ssir.org/articles/entry/in_search_of_the_hybrid_ideal
- Bowser, A., Shilton, K., Preece, J., & Warrick, E. (2020). Accounting for privacy in citizen science: Ethical research in a context of openness. In K. Vohland et al. (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 247–268). Springer.
- Ceccaroni, L., Bibby, J., Roger, E., Flemons, P., Michael, K., Fagan, L., & Oliver, J. L. (2019). Opportunities and risks for citizen science in the age of artificial intelligence. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 4(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.241>
- Dahlhausen, K., Krebs, B. L., Watters, J. V., & Ganz, H. H. (2016). Crowdfunding campaigns help researchers launch projects and generate outreach. *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education*, 17(1), 32–37.
- DITOs Consortium (2018). D6.6 Innovation Management Plan: Making citizen science work. Grant Agreement No. 709443. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5bfa59008&appId=PPGMS>
- ECSA Position Paper (2024). Citizen science for the future of Europe. European Citizen Science Association. Available at: <https://citizensciencefp10.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/PositionPaper.pdf>
- European Commission (2022). Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives: Policy and practice – Final report. DG RTD. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/63baa6bb-d359-11ed-a05c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- Fortson, L., Crowston, K., Kloetzer, L., & Ponti, M. (Eds.) (2024). Special collection: The future of artificial intelligence and citizen science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*.
- Foster, W. L., Kim, P., & Christiansen, B. (2009). Ten nonprofit funding models. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, Spring 2009. Available at: <https://law.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/SSIR-Ten-Funding-Models-edit.pdf>

- Fraisl, D., See, L., Fritz, S., Haklay, M., & McCallum, I. (2025). Leveraging the collaborative power of AI and citizen science for sustainable development. *Nature Sustainability*, 8(2), 125-132. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01489-2>
- Francisco, I., Carneiro, S., & Moreira, T. (2025). Deliverable 4.3: Mapping of citizen science funding models. CROPS project, Grant Agreement No. 101131696.
- Francisco, I., Carneiro, S., & Moreira, T. (2026). Deliverable 4.4: Protocol for mobilising funding and ensuring sustainability – Preliminary version. CROPS project, Grant Agreement No. 101131696.
- François, K., & Goi, H. (2023). Business model for scaling social impact towards sustainability by social entrepreneurs. *Sustainability*, 15, 14027. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151814027>
- Haklay, M., et al. (2021). What is citizen science? The challenges of definition. In K. Vohland et al. (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 13–33). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_1
- IMPETUS Project (2023). Policy brief: How citizen science data can help public institutions and civil society organisations make better local decisions. GA 101058677. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10143183>
- IMPETUS Project (2024). Policy brief: The role of citizen science in European water management and policy. GA 101058677. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14887737>
- Kieslinger, B., Schäfer, T., Heigl, F., Dörler, D., Richter, A., & Bonn, A. (2018). The challenge of evaluation: An open framework for evaluating citizen science activities. In S. Hecker et al. (Eds.), *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy* (pp. 81–95). UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>
- Kim, P., Perreault, G., & Foster, W. (2011). Finding your funding model: A practical approach to nonprofit sustainability. The Bridgespan Group. Available at: <https://www.bridgespan.org/insights/nonprofit-financial-sustainability/finding-your-funding-model-a-practical-approach-to>
- Lotfian, M., Claramunt, C., Berti Suman, A., et al. (2026). A vision for responsible AI integration in citizen science. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 13, Article 145. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-026-06594-5>
- Mendell, M. (2010). Reflections on the evolving landscape of social enterprise in North America. *Policy and Society*, 29(3), 243–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2010.07.003>
- Mitra, J., Sokołowicz, M., Weisenfeld, U., Kurczewska, A., & Tegtmeier, S. (2020). Citizen entrepreneurship: A conceptual picture of the inclusion, integration and engagement of citizens in the entrepreneurial process. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Emerging Economies*, 6(2), 242–260. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2393957520936884>
- Mollick, E. (2014). The dynamics of crowdfunding: An exploratory study. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2013.06.005>

- Moreira, T., Carneiro, S., Caria, M., & Francisco, I. (2026). Deliverable 3.3: CROPS guidelines for stakeholder engagement. CROPS project, Grant Agreement No. 101131696.
- OECD (2025). Embedding citizen science into research policy. *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 175*. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/a1cfb1a8-en>
- Pelacho, M., Ferrer, G., Sanz, F., Tarancón, A., & Clemente-Gallardo, J. (2021). *Landscape study on funding schemes for Social Sciences and the Humanities' Citizen Science activities* (COESO Deliverable D4.1, Grant Agreement No. 101006325). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/5137247>
- Radicchi, A., et al. (2023). Thematic report: Scaling up citizen science. Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science Initiatives. European Commission, DG RTD.
- Sauermann, H., Franzoni, C., & Shafi, K. (2019). Crowdfunding scientific research: Descriptive insights and correlates of funding success. *PLoS ONE*, 14(1), e0208384.
- Sauermann, H., Vohland, K., et al. (2020). Citizen science and sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 49(5), 103978.
- Schürz, S., Kieslinger, B., Holocher, T., & Ros, M. (2026). *Beyond Participation: Citizen Science, Policy Impact and Economic Value*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20084379>
- Science Europe (2018). Briefing paper on citizen science. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925778>
- Shirk, J. L., et al. (2012). Public participation in scientific research: A framework for deliberate design. *Ecology and Society*, 17(2), 29. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-04705-170229>
- Smaniotto, C. (2022). Policy brief: Funding citizen science in the social sciences and humanities. COESO Project, Grant Agreement No. 101006325.
- Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M., Ceccaroni, L., et al. (2021). Impact assessment of citizen science: State of the art and guiding principles for a consolidated approach. *Sustainability Science*, 16, 1683–1699. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00959-2>

10.1 Additional sources consulted

- Armstrong, R., & Grobbelaar, S. (2022). Sustainable business models for social enterprises in developing countries: A conceptual framework. *Management Review Quarterly*, 73, 787–840. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-022-00260-1>
- Chapman, C., Pocock, M., Parr, J., Brown, M., Letheren, B., & UKEOF Citizen Science Working Group. (2020). *Data management planning for citizen science*. UK Environmental Observation Framework. <https://ukeof.org.uk/sites/default/files/2023-09/UKEOF-data-guidance-booklet-web.pdf>

- David, P. A., Hall, B. H., & Toole, A. A. (2000). Is public R&D a complement or substitute for private R&D? A review of the econometric evidence. *Research Policy*, 29(4–5), 497–529.
- Defourny, J., Nyssens, M., & Brolis, O. (2020). Testing social enterprise models across the world: Evidence from the ICSEM project. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 50(2), 420–440. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0899764020959470>
- Eitzel, M. V., et al. (2017). Citizen science terminology matters: Exploring key terms. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.96>
- Joint Nature Conservation Committee. (2024, January 11). *Monitoring for nature recovery and local change*. <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/citizen-science-for-local-change/>
- Joint Nature Conservation Committee. (2024, January 11). *Monitoring for nature recovery and local change: Survey methods and tools*. <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/citizen-science-survey-methods-and-tools/>
- Sprinks, J., et al. (2024). Supporting the upscaling of citizen science to address global challenges. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 9(1).
- Sprinks, J., et al. (2026). *Deliverable 3.1: Protocols for upscaling*. CROPS project, Grant Agreement No. 101131696.
- UK Environmental Observation Framework. (n.d.-a). *Citizen Science Working Group*. Retrieved June 29, 2026, from <https://ukeof.org.uk/our-work/citizen-science>
- UK Environmental Observation Framework. (n.d.-b). *Understanding opportunities, cost and benefits of citizen science*. Retrieved June 29, 2026, from <https://ukeof.org.uk/our-work/citizen-science/cswg-outputs/opps-costs-benefits-2016>
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. (2026, March 9). *Quality assurance handbook and toolkit for participatory science projects*. <https://www.epa.gov/participatory-science/quality-assurance-handbook-and-toolkit-participatory-science-projects>
- Vohland, K., et al. (Eds.). (2021). *The science of citizen science*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4>

Annexes

Annexes

ANNEX A

Interview Protocols

Semi-structured questions used in the two CROPS expert-interview rounds.

A.1 Interview protocol, round 1 (semi-structured)

Introduction: About the CROPS project; goal of the interview; consent request.

Questions

1. Could you briefly tell me about your experience with citizen science initiatives and your role in relation to funding?
2. Based on your experience, what would be the key elements of an ideal protocol to help CS initiatives mobilise sustainable funding? What steps and recommendations do you usually take to mobilise funds?
3. What funding models have you observed in CS initiatives?
4. What are, in your opinion, the best practices of in-kind contributions or non-monetary resources in CS (e.g. volunteer work, data sharing)?
5. Could you describe the most successful and effective sustainability approaches and strategies you have encountered to keep a CS project running?
6. What are the most significant challenges when securing funding for CS projects?
7. Have you observed links between Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and funding acquisition?
8. Do you believe that existing funding policies/programmes, both at the EU and national levels, adequately support CS initiatives?
9. In your opinion, how accessible is the existing funding landscape to CS?
10. What recommendations do you have for improving the current funding landscape for CS initiatives, keeping in mind project sustainability?

A.2 Interview protocol, round 2

Introduction: About the CROPS project; purpose of the second interview round; consent request. The questions below are reproduced in indicative form; interviews were semi-structured and adapted to each interviewee's role.

Questions

1. Could you describe your organisation or platform and how it is currently funded?
2. Which funding models have worked best for you in practice, and which have not?
3. How do you approach sustainability beyond the current grant or funding cycle?
4. Where revenue is generated, what is the mechanism, and how do you keep it compatible with citizen science principles?
5. What has your experience been with private-sector engagement, sponsorship, or commercial partnerships?
6. If you have used crowdfunding or community fundraising, what made it work or not work?
7. How do you fund the operational systems behind participation: coordination, IT, data validation, and community support?
8. What advice would you give a project trying to move from single-grant dependence to a more sustainable model?

ANNEX B

Survey Instruments

The two CROPS surveys (Task 3.2) underpinning the funding-model and scalability evidence.

B.1 CROPS Case Study Survey

The CROPS Case Study Survey was developed under Task 3.2 to characterise CS initiatives across Europe, including their funding sources, sustainability mechanisms, and scaling experience. Its results are reported in CROPS D4.3 (Mapping of CS Funding Models) and inform the funding categories and case-study evidence used in this protocol. The instrument is held in the CROPS project repository.

B.2 Scalability Survey

The Scalability Survey, also developed under Task 3.2, examined the conditions under which CS initiatives scale (out, up, deep, or down) and the resources this requires. Where its findings

are used in this protocol, they are drawn from the consolidated analysis reported in CROPS D4.3 and D3.1. The instrument is held in the CROPS project repository.

ANNEX C

Practical Business-Model Setup Guidance

Expands the six business models in Table 6.1 (Section 6.4). None suits every project - choose based on the Step 2 diagnosis and the Step 3 fit assessment.

1. Open data plus paid services

Target users	Public bodies, NGOs, and researchers who need analysis rather than raw data.
Revenue	Tailored reports, dashboards, policy briefs, commissioned workshops.
Preconditions	A trusted dataset and the analytical capacity to interpret it.
Pitfall	Paid services must never create exclusive access to citizen-generated data; the core stays open.

2. Data quality and certification

Target users	Agencies and companies that need assurance about data they rely on.
Revenue	Validation, QA reports, certified data feeds, methodology audits.
Preconditions	Transparent, documented quality processes.
Pitfall	Credibility collapses if data limitations are hidden; certify honestly or not at all.

3. Open-source platform plus hosted services

Target users	Other projects and institutions that want the tool without running it.
Revenue	Managed hosting, maintenance, custom deployment, support.
Preconditions	A genuinely reusable platform and clear documentation.

Pitfall	Protect the open core from client capture through explicit governance.
----------------	--

4. Knowledge brokerage

Target users	Organisations new to participatory methods.
Revenue	Training, consultancy, participation design, impact-measurement support.
Preconditions	Demonstrable expertise and teaching capacity.
Pitfall	Service work can quietly displace the research and community commitments that gave the project its credibility.

5. Co-production cost model

Target users	Public funders weighing CS against professional-only monitoring.
Revenue	Public funding justified by cost-efficiency and added civic value.
Preconditions	Validated data and a credible cost comparison.
Pitfall	Do not let the project be framed as cheap labour; the argument is efficiency plus participation value, not substitution.

6. Federated commons or infrastructure membership

Target users	A community of projects sharing standards and tools.
Revenue	Membership fees, institutional contributions, co-governance contributions.
Preconditions	Critical mass and shared governance.
Pitfall	Guard against governance capture by the largest contributors.

A practical sequence

Confirm which part of the work is genuinely valuable to someone who would pay; keep the citizen-generated core open; price the service layer, not the data; and write the governance terms down before taking the first payment.

Setting up any of these models involves legal, financial, and strategic choices that fall outside most research teams’ day-to-day experience. Projects do not need to make them unassisted: host institutions’ technology-transfer or innovation offices, national CS platforms, and innovation consultancies (including INOVA+, the developer of this protocol) can support the design and validation of a business model before resources are committed.

ANNEX D

The Funding Toolkit

Templates and checklists referenced throughout the protocol, organised by project phase: design and value definition, funding readiness, governance and ethics, impact assessment, and long-term sustainability.

D.1 Theory of Change template

Element	Guiding questions
Problem or challenge	What societal, scientific, environmental, educational, or policy challenge does the project address?
Target groups	Who is affected? Who should be involved? Who will benefit?
Project objective	What change does the project aim to contribute to?
Inputs	What resources are needed (funding, staff, partners, infrastructure, data, tools, community relationships)?
Activities	What will the project do (data collection, training, workshops, fieldwork, platform development, policy engagement)?
Outputs	What direct products will be produced (datasets, reports, tools, events, training materials, dashboards)?
Outcomes	What changes are expected in knowledge, skills, behaviour, awareness, relationships, policy, or community capacity?

Element	Guiding questions
Long-term impact	What broader scientific, social, environmental, governance, educational, or economic impact is expected?
Assumptions	What assumptions must hold true for the project to succeed?
Risks	What could prevent the expected change from happening?
Evidence and indicators	How will the project know whether change is happening?

D.2 Business Model Canvas (adapted for CS)

Canvas area	Guiding questions
Value proposition	What value does the project create, and for whom?
Key beneficiaries	Who benefits (citizens, communities, researchers, public authorities, schools, companies, funders)?
Key partners	Which organisations are essential?
Key activities	What activities are necessary to deliver the project?
Key resources	What resources are required (staff, volunteers, data infrastructure, expertise, community trust)?
Stakeholder relationships	How will the project build and maintain relationships?
Channels	Through which channels will the project reach its audiences?
Cost structure	What are the main costs?
Funding and revenue streams	What funding sources or revenue streams are possible?
Sustainability risks	Which parts of the model are fragile?

D.3 Value Proposition Canvas

Fill-in template - complete one row per stakeholder group.

Stakeholder group	Needs, priorities or problems	Value offered by the CS project	Evidence or proof
Citizen scientists / participants			
Local communities			
Researchers			
Public authorities			
Private funders or companies			
Schools or educational institutions			
NGOs and civil society			
Funders			

D.4 SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
What does the project already do well?	What limits the project’s capacity?

Opportunities	Threats
What external opportunities could support the project?	What external risks could undermine it?

Opportunities	Threats

Follow-up questions: Which strengths support a funding application? Which weaknesses must be addressed first? Which opportunities should be prioritised in the next 6 to 12 months? Which threats require mitigation?

D.5 Funding Readiness Checklist

Readiness area	Guiding question	Status
Mission and ethics fit	Does the opportunity align with the project’s purpose, participant rights, and community priorities?	Yes / No / To develop
Project-stage fit	Is the project mature enough for this funding route?	
Role fit	Should the project lead, join, provide a service, or apply for cascading funding?	
Value proposition fit	Can the project explain clearly what it offers and why the funder should care?	
Scientific rationale	Is the research question, evidence gap, and methodology clearly defined?	
Capacity fit	Can the team manage the application, delivery, and reporting?	
Partnership fit	Does the consortium have the right mix of skills?	
Budget realism	Does the budget include the true costs of coordination, communication, evaluation, and IT?	
Evidence fit	Are impact metrics and monitoring processes in place?	
Sustainability fit	Is there a plan for what happens when the funding ends?	

D.6 Funding Pipeline and Call Tracker

Field	Description
Call or opportunity name	
Funder	
Deadline	
Budget range	
Fit with project mission	High / Medium / Low
Stage suitability	Early / Established / Mature
Role	Lead / Partner / Cascading / Service
Contact person	
Status	Identified / Preparing / Submitted / Awarded / Rejected
Notes	

D.5 Funding Readiness Checklist

Readiness area	Guiding question	Status
Mission and ethics fit	Does the opportunity align with the project’s purpose, participant rights, and community priorities?	Yes / No / To develop
Project-stage fit	Is the project mature enough for this funding route?	
Role fit	Should the project lead, join, provide a service, or apply for cascading funding?	
Value proposition fit	Can the project explain clearly what it offers and why the funder should care?	

Readiness area	Guiding question	Status
Scientific rationale	Is the research question, evidence gap, and methodology clearly defined?	
Capacity fit	Can the team manage the application, delivery, and reporting?	
Partnership fit	Does the consortium have the right mix of skills?	
Budget realism	Does the budget include the true costs of coordination, communication, evaluation, and IT?	
Evidence fit	Are impact metrics and monitoring processes in place?	
Sustainability fit	Is there a plan for what happens when the funding ends?	

D.6 Funding Pipeline and Call Tracker

Field	Description
Call or opportunity name	
Funder	
Deadline	
Budget range	
Fit with project mission	High / Medium / Low
Stage suitability	Early / Established / Mature
Role	Lead / Partner / Cascading / Service
Contact person	
Status	Identified / Preparing / Submitted / Awarded / Rejected

Field	Description
Notes	

D.7 Data Management Plan template

A citizen science Data Management Plan should be proportionate to the project but cover the following.

Element	What to record
Data collected	Types, formats, volumes, and collection methods
Roles and responsibilities	Who collects, validates, stores, and stewards the data
Quality assurance	Validation steps, error handling, and how data limitations are documented
Storage and security	Where data is held, backup arrangements, and access controls
Legal and ethical basis	GDPR lawful basis, participant consent, and handling of personal data
Sharing and openness	What is published openly, under which licence, and any embargoes
Participant rights	Consent for reuse, including commercial reuse, and withdrawal procedures
AI and automated processing	Any automated validation or analysis, with transparency about its use
Long-term preservation	Where data lives after the grant ends, and who maintains it

The plan should be written at the proposal stage, not after award, and revisited whenever the funding model changes.

D.8 Ethics and CS Principles Checklist

This checklist draws on the ECSA Ten Principles of Citizen Science, GDPR requirements, and the ethical issues that arise specifically in funding relationships.

- Participants are genuine contributors to knowledge, not unpaid labour, and their contribution is acknowledged.
- Consent covers how data will be used, including any commercial reuse, and participants can withdraw.

- Personal data is handled on a clear GDPR lawful basis, minimised, and secured.
- Data ownership and access terms are explicit, and citizen-generated data is not placed behind exclusive paywalls.
- Conflicts of interest, especially with private funders, are declared and managed.
- Publication and communication remain independent of funder influence.
- The project guards against greenwashing, citizen-science-washing, and extractive partnerships.
- Benefits flow back to participants and communities, not only to the host institution or funder.
- Vulnerable groups, including minors, are protected, with appropriate safeguards in school and community settings.

Any point that cannot be answered positively should be resolved before money changes hands, particularly in private and hybrid models.

D.9 MICS (Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science) summary

MICS (Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science) is an EU-developed framework and online platform for assessing CS impact across five domains: society, economy, environment, science and technology, and governance. It provides indicators and a structured method for planning and reporting impact. For funder communication, MICS is useful because it lets a project state expected and achieved impact in recognised categories rather than anecdotes. Projects can use the MICS platform (mics.tools) to select domain-relevant indicators at the planning stage and report against them later. Build the chosen indicators into the evaluation plan from the start (see Step 6).

D.10 SROI (Social Return on Investment) guidance

Social Return on Investment (SROI) expresses the social, environmental, and economic value a project creates relative to the resources invested, often as a ratio of value to cost. It works by identifying stakeholders, mapping outcomes, assigning proxy financial values to those outcomes, and discounting for what would have happened anyway. For CS, SROI can translate hard-to-monetise benefits (volunteer learning, better environmental decisions, community cohesion) into terms funders recognise. Use it carefully: the proxies are estimates, and an honest SROI states its assumptions. Even a simple, well-documented SROI narrative can strengthen a funding case where the indirect value of CS would otherwise go unstated (see the value-creation discussion in Step 6 and Schürz et al., 2026).

D.11 CS Funding Pitch Deck template

Slide	Content
1 Title	Project name, tagline, team
2 Problem	What societal, scientific, or environmental challenge does the project address?
3 Solution	What does the project do and how?
4 Evidence	What results, data, or outcomes has the project produced?
5 Value proposition	What value does the project offer to this funder specifically?
6 Participation model	Who participates and how? What is the community base?
7 Impact	What scientific, social, environmental, or economic impact has been achieved or is expected?
8 Funding need	What is the funding request and what will it cover?
9 Sustainability	How will the project sustain itself beyond this funding?

Slide	Content
10 Team and partners	Who delivers the project and who supports it?
11 Call to action	What is the specific next step requested from the funder or partner?

D.12 Sustainability and Transition Plan template

Element	Guiding questions
Core functions to sustain	Which activities, data, infrastructure, or relationships must continue beyond the funding period?
Functions that can be reduced	Which activities can be scaled down or paused without losing core value?
Functions that can be transferred	Which activities could be taken over by another organisation, institution, or community?
Functions that can responsibly end	Which activities have achieved their purpose and can conclude?
Institutional host	Who will maintain the project long-term (university, NGO, public body, platform, municipality)?
Data and infrastructure continuity	Who will pay for hosting, maintenance, data security, and user support?
Community continuity	How will participant relationships, feedback loops, and community trust be maintained?
Transition timeline	What is the timeline for preparing the transition, and who is responsible for each step?
Contingency	What happens if the planned transition fails?

D.13 Partnership Due Diligence Checklist (for private and hybrid funding)

Before accepting private or hybrid funding, assess each potential partner against the following criteria.

Area	Question	Assessment
Mission alignment	Does the partner’s core activity conflict with the project’s scientific or civic mission?	Red flag / Caution / Clear
Sector screening	Is the partner’s sector associated with activities that would damage participant trust (e.g. fossil fuels, tobacco, arms)?	
Data governance	Will the partner access citizen-generated data? Under what conditions? Is participant consent in place?	
Publication independence	Does the agreement protect the project’s right to publish findings, including unfavourable ones?	
Branding and visibility	Are terms around logos, naming, and public communication clear and acceptable?	
Greenwashing risk	Is the partner likely to use the CS partnership primarily for reputation without acting on evidence?	
Benefit-sharing	If commercial value is generated from citizen data, is there a fair benefit-sharing arrangement?	
Participant transparency	Will participants be informed about the partnership, its terms, and the partner’s identity?	
Exit terms	Are there pre-agreed terms for ending the partnership if ethical or mission concerns arise?	
Conflicts of interest	Are there personal, institutional, or financial conflicts of interest within the project team?	

D.14 Post-Grant Continuity Checklist

Timing	Action	Status
12+ months before grant end	Identify which core functions must continue (data hosting, community management, platform, coordination)	
	Identify the most suitable long-term institutional host	
	Begin conversations with the host about base funding or institutional embedding	
	Assess which activities can be reduced, transferred, or responsibly ended	
9 months before	Map potential follow-on funding sources	
	Prepare a sustainability case document showing demand, outputs, and partnerships	
	Document all operational processes, technical infrastructure, and community management practices	
6 months before	Submit follow-on funding applications	
	Confirm data hosting, domain, server, and technical support arrangements	
	Communicate transition plans to participants, partners, and stakeholders	
3 months before	Finalise handover to the institutional host or transition arrangement	
	Ensure all data, code, documentation, and community contacts are accessible	
	Publish final outputs and datasets as open resources	
After grant end	Monitor whether the transition is working; adjust if needed	
	Maintain a minimal communication channel with the community	

ANNEX E

Anonymised List of Interviewees and Workshop Participants

Affiliations and areas of expertise for the experts consulted across both interview rounds

Expert interviews, Round 1 (2025)

	Affiliation	Area of expertise
1	IMPETUS	CS project coordination; prizes and awards; private-public partnerships
2	MMOS (Massively Multiplayer Online Science)	Gaming industry partnerships; private-sector CS models
3	Hewlett Foundation	Philanthropic funding; grant-making for CS
4	BioDiversity4All	National CS platform management; community funding
5	Telraam	Technical infrastructure; EU project funding
6	University of Nottingham	Crowdfunding; volunteer motivation; CS engagement
7	UCL	CS history; policy; participatory research design
8	Platoniq Foundation	Civic crowdfunding; match-funding models

	Affiliation	Area of expertise
9	BioDiversity4All	Membership models; environmental CS sustainability

Expert interviews, Round 2 (2026)

	Affiliation / Role	Area of expertise
10	Zooniverse	Large-scale platform sustainability; corporate volunteering; hybrid models
11	OutBe	CS as a service; private-sector engagement; paradigm shift in CS funding
12	Earthwatch	Corporate partnerships; field-based CS; environmental monitoring funding
13	NWO (Dutch Research Council)	Public research funding design; open science; dedicated CS pathways
14	Experiment.com	Science crowdfunding; microgrants; proof-of-concept models
15	COESO / VERA	SSH citizen science; funding landscape; matchmaking platforms
16	IES-SBS	Social innovation and social-sciences perspective on CS funding

	Affiliation / Role	Area of expertise
17	University of Geneva	Academic perspective on citizen science and open science

ANNEX F

Consolidated List of CROPS Empirical Data Sources

All evidence sources behind D4.5, with how each was used.

Source type	Source	Date	How used in D4.5
Expert interviews, Round 1	9 semi-structured interviews (see Annex E)	May–November 2025	Primary evidence for all chapters; also used in D4.3
Expert interviews, Round 2	8 semi-structured interviews (see Annex E)	April–May 2026	Primary evidence for all chapters
Mutual learning workshop	Encontro Nacional de Ciência Cidadã, Oeiras	November 2025	Funding challenges, sustainability strategies
Mutual learning workshop	ECSA 2026 workshop, Oulu	March 2026	Collaborative refinement of the protocol
Expert roundtable 1	CROPS Roundtable on Mobilising Funding	April 2026	Implementation feedback on Step 5
Expert roundtable 2	CROPS Roundtable on Mobilising Funding	May 2026	Final validation
Conference participation	CAPS 2026, closing plenary on funding	2026	Infrastructure costs; volunteer labour; funder behaviour
Validation workshops	CROPS WP2 framework-validation sessions	2025–2026	Sustainability mechanisms and risks from case-study projects

Source type	Source	Date	How used in D4.5
Deliverable	D4.3, Mapping of CS Funding Models	December 2025	Funding taxonomy, empirical mapping (Step 1)
Deliverable	D4.4, Preliminary Version of this protocol	M24	Baseline draft; stakeholder feedback incorporated
Deliverable	D3.3, Guidelines for Stakeholder Engagement	February 2026	Cross-reference for engagement strategies

ANNEX G

Glossary

Key terms used throughout the protocol.

Term	Definition
Cascading grants / FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties: sub-grants from larger EU projects distributed to smaller initiatives with simplified requirements.
Co-created project	A CS project in which citizens are involved in formulating research questions, designing the study, or interpreting results, not only in data collection.
Contributory project	A CS project in which citizens primarily collect data within a researcher-designed framework.
Corporate social entrepreneurship (CSE)	A model in which social value creation is embedded into the core strategy of a company, not limited to peripheral philanthropy (Austin and Reficco, 2009).
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility: discretionary programmes through which companies support social or environmental causes.
Double value creation	The simultaneous pursuit of financial performance and positive societal impact, treated as mutually reinforcing (Austin and Reficco, 2009).
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance: a set of criteria used by investors and companies to assess sustainability performance.

Term	Definition
Hybrid organisation	An organisation that pursues social and commercial objectives simultaneously (Battilana et al., 2012).
MICS	Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science: a framework for structured impact assessment across scientific, social, environmental, governance, and economic dimensions.
Mission drift	The gradual erosion of an organisation’s social mission under pressure from commercial or financial incentives.
SROI	Social Return on Investment: a method for measuring broader social and economic value beyond financial returns.
Upscaling	Extending the reach, impact, or scope of a CS initiative (scaling out, up, deep, or down).

ANNEX H

Platforms for Networking, Visibility and Funding Intelligence

Supports Step 6 (Section 7.1). Platforms for finding funding calls, building visibility, and connecting with partners.

Platform	Description	Link
European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)	Entry point for contacts with CS actors; projects directory; policy advocacy	ecsa.ngo
EU Funding & Tenders Portal	Central portal for Horizon Europe and EU Missions; partner search tool	ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders
Citizen Science Global Partnership (CSGP)	Regional and national CS organisations, research groups, NGOs, policy actors	citizenscienceglobal.org
SciStarter	Showcases CS projects and resources; allows posting new projects	scistarter.org
EU-Citizen.Science	Large directory of CS projects, tools, training material, and organisations	citizenscience.eu

Platform	Description	Link
CitSci-X Explorer	JRC platform listing CS projects by scope, domain, and geography	ec-jrc.github.io/citsci-explorer
VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation)	CS hub for SSH; matchmaking tools and funding-opportunity finder (Fundit)	vera.operas-eu.org/en/fundit
Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences (AAPS)	Promotes participatory science; connects scientists with the public	participatorysciences.org
Citizen Science Association (CSA) / CSA Connect	Professional network for CS practitioners; resources, events, collaboration	citizenscience.org
Zooniverse	Largest platform for crowdsourced research projects	zooniverse.org
iNaturalist / GBIF	Global platforms for biodiversity observations	inaturalist.org / gbif.org
Scivil	Flemish knowledge centre for CS; matchmaking for research, NGOs, education	scivil.be/en/partners
EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)	Open science tools and services for collaborative research across Europe	eosc-portal.eu
Bürger schaffen Wissen	German CS portal for public engagement and research collaboration	buergerschaffenwissen.de
Österreich forscht	Austrian CS platform connecting volunteers with research projects	citizen-science.at
Schweiz forscht	Swiss CS platform for research collaboration and public participation	schweizforscht.ch
ACSA	Australian Citizen Science Association; promotes CS through collaboration	citizenscience.org.au
Anecdata.org	Web portal for environmental science, biology, and public health CS	anecdata.org
Cochrane Crowd	Crowdsourcing platform for evidence-based healthcare research	crowd.cochrane.org

Platform	Description	Link
CitizenScience.gov	US government portal for CS projects and funding opportunities	citizenscience.gov

